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Standardization landscape, needs and gaps for the VHT

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Executive summary

The standards document is the Task 2.3 of the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) of the EDITH (Ecosystem Digital Twins in Healthcare) project. It describes the current landscape of standards, terminologies and guidelines for biomedical data, metadata, simulation models and workflows relevant for the definition, implementation, and simulation of Digital Twins in Healthcare (DTHs). It comprises both official as well as community standards and lists the available standards and terminologies describing the modelling process, the integration of domain-specific medical research data with routine data from electronic health records, the documentation of data provenance, the validation process for biomedical, physiological, bio-signaling and other healthcare data and models.

In addition, the document reveals needs and gaps in the current standards landscape to drive the further development of such standards. Therefore, remarks and comments on how to improve existing standards or on areas for which standards are still missing are very welcome.

T2.3 Analysing current landscape of standards, identifying needs and gaps.

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1. Standardisation initiatives and committees of standard defining organisations (SDOs) relevant for Virtual Human Twins (VHTs) for healthcare

1.1 Technical standard defining organisations

The most important standard defining organisation (SDOs) for technical standards are the International Standards Organisation (ISO) with its Technical Committees 215 (Health Informatics) and 276 (Biotechnology) and the CEN / CENELEC with its technical committee 251 (Health Informatics). In addition, there are several other institutions, societies and authorities defining standards relevant for VHTs. Beside that there are also some grass-root communities like **COMBINE**, the **Avicenna Alliance** and the Genome Alliance for Genomics and Health (**GA4GH**). A full list of SDOs defining technical standards is given in *Table 1* in the annex.

1.2 Clinical standard defining organisations

For the definition of clinical standards there are also several institutes, organizations, and initiatives. One of the most prominent of them is the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (**CDISC**). A comprehensive list of SDOs relevant for defining clinical standards is given in *Table 2* in the annex.

2. Standards for data formats, data integration and data input into models

To ease the access to information about and specifications of the standards we defined the EDITH FAIRSharing [Sansone et al., 2019] collection (<https://fairsharing.org/4787>) containing all recommended data, metadata and modelling standards for the construction, validation and usage of the VHT and its parts, as well as relevant standards for data/model quality, modelling processes and workflows. FAIRSharing is a repository for data and metadata standards and terminologies in the biomedical domain. It also describes their use by databases and policies and allows to group together standards belonging to a project in so-called collections.

The **ISO 20691:2022**¹ standard “*Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences*” requires that the data in the life sciences shall be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). Therefore, the data used in models and simulations of the human digital twin should at least encompass the information described in the minimum information standards and follow the FAIR² principles. For being FAIR, the data must have a unique ID, must be linkable, must have an assigned licence and must be annotated by metadata describing for instance the disease, the tissue, the cell type, and the used modelling parameters.

Other requirements described in ISO 20691:2022 are about the consistent formatting and documentation of data, models, and metadata as well as the requirements concerning storing, sharing, accessing, interoperability and reuse of data, models, and metadata in the life sciences.

The ISO 20691:2022 standard acts as a reference framework or hub standard for other life science data and integration standards. It describes the requirements and rules for applying standards for formatting, description, and documentation of data types in the life sciences and contains a catalogue of criteria and requirements for interoperable life science data formats and semantic data description standards.

¹<https://www.iso.org/standard/68848.html#:~:text=This%20document%20specifies%20requirements%20for,human%20biological%20research%20and%20development.>

² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

The **annex A of ISO 20691:2022** contains a list of common recommended formats for life science data and the **annex B** contains a list of minimal reporting standards for data, models, and metadata. This set of metadata describes the context of the data and models.

The **ISO 20691 FAIRSharing collection**³ contains a listing of these standard formats, which should be used to represent life science data and to annotate them by ontology terms. This list encompasses data formats for -omics, biochemical and molecular biology methods as well as formats for biological imaging and for computer models of biological systems. That FAIRSharing collection is actively managed and maintained, so that it is always on the last stand.

A further standard is **ISO/TS 9491**⁴ “*Biotechnology — Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalised medicine research*”, which consists of two parts:

Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying, and validating models.

Part 2: Guidelines for implementing computational models in clinical integrated decision support systems.

Another ISO standard is **ISO 4454:2022**⁵ “*Genomics informatics – Phenopackets: A format for phenotypic data exchange*”, which standardised the description of phenotypic information.

The **ISO 23494 series**⁶ “*Biotechnology – Provenance information model for biological material and data*” describes how to document the provenance information for biological data and samples.

2.1 Data integration

Data integration combines data from different sources like Electronic Health Records (**EHR**), life-style data, environmental and registry data, molecular -omics data, laboratory data, imaging data, biosignal, intensive care vital sign data and other medical relevant sorts of data. Data integration can be done either on the individual level or on the variable level.

Individual level integration is required for personalised models and means that all available data for an individual patient are brought together for the model building and simulation tasks.

It was demonstrated that it's possible to integrate several modelling frameworks (agent-based models, ordinary differential equations, stochastic reaction systems, constraint-based models, solid-body physics and spatial diffusion) into a composite model. But a standard for such an integration of different models into a multiscale model is still missing, even though there are some proposals for such integrative frameworks [Agmon et al., 2022 and Masison et al., 2021].

The **ISO/DIS 14199**⁷ standard “*Health informatics — Information models — Biomedical Research Integrated Domain Group (BRIDG) Model*” is a domain model for data interchange that enables semantic interoperability and intends to bridge between biomedical, clinical research and routine healthcare data. It can be seen as a meta-standard and can be used as a starting point and blueprint for the integration of modelling and simulation data with other health data and how to make them interoperable.

³ <https://fairsharing.org/3533>

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/83516.html>

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79991.html>

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/80715.html>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/83433.html>

2.2 Harmonised access to data across resources

Currently there are no harmonised strategies for data access since the data protection laws are varying between the countries and can even vary from federal state to federal state as in Germany.

What shall be used are strategies to control the access to restricted (e.g., person-related) data by researchers. Such harmonised Data Access Agreements (**hDAAs**) are still missing now.

2.3 Standards for medical imaging

For medical imaging there are three important standards. The first one is the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (**DICOM**), which is the most used data structure in health care, and which stores the data as 2D layers. The Brain Imaging Data Structure (**BIDS**) is a group of standards defined by the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility (**INCF**) and is mainly used in neuroscience/neuroimaging research. For several special imaging techniques extensions to BIDS are available, which contain mainly metadata describing features for these special techniques. OpenNeuro⁸ is a platform for validation of BIDS data sets. A third group of standards were defined by the Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (**NIFTI**) and stores the data in a true 3D volume format. *Table 3* in the annex gives an overview about these formats and their extensions / descendants.

To standardize medical imaging workflows, it's necessary to describe the medical images with a set of standardized features. Such a set of 169 radiomics features was defined by the Image Biomarker Standardization Initiative (**IBSI**) [Zwanenburg et al., 2020].

2.4 Standard formats for electro- and neurophysiology, biosignal and vital sign data

Since the annexes of ISO 20691 and ISO/TS 9491 list mainly systems biology formats, in the following some formats for physiology / biomedicine are listed. There is a plenitude of formats in the areas of electrophysiology, **biosignal** and time series of **vital sign data** (e.g., body temperature, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, pulse rate, respiration rate, oxygen saturation, BMI...) recorded in intensive care. Many of them are proprietary formats defined by medical device manufacturers. Therefore, in *Table 4* of the annex only formats supported by Standard Defining Organizations (SDOs), community standards, or formats, which are at least de facto standards, are listed.

An example for such formats is the European Data Format (**EDF / EDF+**), a format for exchange and storage of multichannel biological and physical signals, e.g., from polysomnography (PSG), echocardiography (ECG), electroencephalography (EEG) and electromyography (EMG). An alternative would be the General Data Format (**GDF**), which is also used for biomedical signals, like e.g., EEG and ECG data. For neurophysiology data the Neurodata Without Borders:Neurophysiology (**NWB:N 2.0**) and for heart electrophysiological and electroanatomic mapping the Open ElectroPhysiology (**OpenEP**) format are recommended. Scalable Open Network Architecture TemplAte (**SONATA**) is used for large-scale modelling of neuronal brain network models and their simulation output. The WaveForm DataBase (**WFDB**) is the format used by the **PhysioNet** (physio.net) repository and a combination of the MIT format and EDF / EDF+. The **MIMIC-III** ('Medical Information Mart for Intensive Care') and **MIMIC-IV** contain anonymized datasets from patients admitted to critical care units and electronic health record datasets.

The problem is that several of these standard formats encode similar things like waveforms, so that it would be desirable to merge them into a more common overarching standard format.

2.5 Other models

Models, which are not stored in a standard format and encoded in a scripting language, e.g., in Mathematica, Matlab / Octave, Python, R, Julia scripts, ... can be executed on the platform either if they have an interface that allows the import/export, respective if the conversion into

⁸ <https://openneuro.org>

one of the aforementioned standard formats is possible, or if the scripts are directly executed **inside** the workflow. Otherwise, the scripts can be generically packed into a **Binary** FHIR resource.

For some kinds of models, e.g., **cellular automata** there are no explicit standards available, but at least some of these models can be described by using the MultiCellML and Morpheus standards. For others, like **Petri net models** there is the **ISO/IEC 15909** standard, but this standard is not biology specific.

2.6 Minimal clinical core datasets

To optimise the research and patient treatment, some minimal clinical datasets, which are specific for a disease were defined. For example, for cancer there is the **mCode⁹ (minimal Common Oncology Data Elements)** HL7-STU (standard in trial use) available. It describes the minimum information, which should be collected in the electronic health records of cancer patients. CodeX (Common Oncology Data Elements Extensions) are FHIR extensions for oncology. Also, for some other diseases, e.g., for multiple sclerosis¹⁰, Parkinson disease and stroke, the definition of minimal clinical datasets is available (see **common data elements catalogue¹¹**).

For some diseases XML-based standard file formats based on such disease-specific common data models for capturing the relevant information are available. Examples are **cMDX** (Clinical Map Document based on XML) for prostate cancer or **BRCAPRO** for breast cancer.

2.7 Best practices guidelines

There are a lot of reporting, **best practices / clinical practice guidelines (CPGs)** and consensus statements. Most of them are specific to the different medical fields. These best practice guidelines are a foundational pillar for evidence-based medicine and guide clinicians in their daily work decisions. Many of these guidelines are related of the use of artificial intelligence (AI) [Wang *et al.* 2023, Crossnohere *et al.* 2022] in medical diagnosis, treatment, or prognosis. Others like **PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses)** are reporting guidelines for systematic reviews of a field [Page *et al.* 2021]. Despite these guidelines are very domain specific, there are some general statements and rules defining what should be reported in these guidelines, e.g. by the **PICAR** statement (**P**opulation, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **A**tttributes of eligible CPGs, **R**ecommendation characteristics) defined by [Johnston *et al.* 2019].

These clinical practice guidelines are also used for meta-analysis. The quality of observational studies is directly influenced by the quality of the captured data. Therefore, the capturing of the meta-variables defined in these guidelines should be done in a standardized and curated way, so that high quality is ensured. Otherwise, the findings of the studies can be easily biased. Often not only the value of the variable itself, but also the severity and duration of how long the value was present, or even the fluctuation of the variable value over time, are important and should be captured in a standardized way.

2.8 Representation of AI-/ML-based models

For AI-based models there are no standardised file formats for the input data available. Since these models are based on big data, they often use hierarchical (.hdf, NetCDF), row-based (.csv, .json), columnar (e.g. Apache Parquet) or other high-performance (e.g. Apache Iceberg) formats as input format for the data used for AI-/ML-based learning.

Most machine learning frameworks define their own model exchange format. For a standardised and interoperable representation and deployment of **machine learning and deep learning models** one of the Open Neural Network Exchange (**ONNX**), Portable Format for Analytics (**PFA**) or Predictive Model Markup Language (**PMML**) standards can be used. Since

⁹ <http://hl7.org/fhir/us/mcode/>

¹⁰ <https://medical-data-models.org/19067?form-lang=en>

¹¹ <https://www.commondataelements.ninds.nih.gov/cde-catalog>

PFA is more flexible than PMML and easier to extend to new algorithms and model types and integrates necessary pre- and post-processing steps, PFA or ONNX shall be used.

The structure and parameters of trained neural networks can be stored and exchanged with the Neural Network Exchange Format (**NNEF**) defined by the Khronos group.

IEC SC42 defines standards for artificial intelligence and the use of synthetic data for artificial intelligence methods¹².

Biolink Model¹³ is a community standard data model for the representation of knowledge graphs, describing how biological entities (genes, diseases, phenotypes, pathways, individuals, substances, ...) are associated with their properties and the relationships between them.

IEEE 2807.5-2022¹⁴ is a standard on **knowledge graphs** in medical diagnosis and treatment.

According to the Report “Artificial Intelligence Standardisation Landscape Update”¹⁵ the following 3 standards are very relevant with respect to the European **AI Act**:

IEEE P7003 Standard for Algorithmic Bias Considerations

IEEE P7001/D4 Draft Standard for Transparency of Autonomous Systems

IEEE 7000 Standard Model Process for Addressing Ethical Concerns during System Design

In addition, there are plenty best practices recommendations for using artificial intelligence, which are specific to the medical field or a disease [Wang et al. 2023, Crossnohere et al. 2022]. A detailed table of AI standards can be found in the Report “Landscape of AI Standards”¹⁶ from the Technical Working Group AI of the CSA project **StandICT.eu**

2.9 Standardisation of VHT workflows

Workflows allow for the fast deployment of the VHT in different computing architectures (such as Cloud and HPC and enables the reproducibility of use cases across different users.

Technically, the use of workflows greatly facilitates the deployment of complex and large use cases in different computing facilities and the generation of intermediate data structures in case the simulation has execution errors or perturbations (as energy outages). They also enable repeatability and reproducibility of use cases while providing a way to integrate provenance of data and privacy by allowing for federated workflows across multiple sites. In the VHT, automatically keeping track of provenance, certainly in relation to the credibility of the output data of a workflow, is a key requirement. Workflows facilitate user understanding of the overall DTH without the need of delving into detailed model documentation and metadata and lowering the learning curve to be able to simulate use cases by themselves.

For example, a workflow recipe for a complex use case for modelling brain tumours combining different types of models, data sources, and output data for a commonly used workflow manager can allow researchers to seamlessly deploy exactly the same use case in the cloud (e.g., AWS and Google Cloud) or in different high-end HPC clusters, e.g., **LUMI**¹⁷ (Large Unified Modern Infrastructure), or **MareNostrum**¹⁸ with minimal amount of work.

There is a plenitude of scientific workflow systems out there¹⁹. Most of them use their own proprietary format for storing the workflow descriptions. Examples are **NFL** (Nextflow), **GXFFORMAT2** (Galaxy) or **SMK** (Snakemake).

¹² <https://iec.ch/blog/isoiec-report-address-synthetic-data-techniques-used-chatgpt-and-other-ai-tools>

¹³ <https://github.com/biolink/biolink-model>

¹⁴ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2807/7525/>

¹⁵ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC131155>

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/5011179>

¹⁷ <https://lumi-supercomputer.eu>

¹⁸ <https://www.bsc.es/marenostrum/marenostrum>

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scientific_workflow_system

Standardised workflow descriptions are the **Common Workflow Language (CWL)**²⁰ based on YAML format and the **Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL)**²¹ of Cromwell, which is more human-readable. Another description language for workflows is **yadage** (YAML adage). Both CWL and yadage describe parameterized workflows based on dynamic directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) of tasks. In yadage these DAGs can be built up at runtime and encapsulated in pre-packaged Docker environments. CWL workflows have no technical restrictions, e.g., for the size of the processed files or the number of tasks which can be run in parallel. For execution under Windows, the **WSL-2** (Windows Subsystem for Linux, Version 2) is needed. **CWLProv** is used for describing workflow provenance information.

CWL can be run locally on desktops, on HPC clusters and in the cloud, it supports containers such as Docker and Apptainer (former Singularity) and is based on the POSIX-CLI standard. It follows the Abstraction, Scaling, Automation and Provenance (**ASAP**) principles and is workflow-engine and vendor neutral [Crusoe et al., 2022].

Even more so, the use of workflows usually but not necessarily involves the division of the work in containerised pieces (such as Docker, Apptainer (former Singularity)). This compartmentalization allows for the decoupling of the complexity of each part of the workflow and its usability in complex use cases. Likewise, these containers facilitate benchmarks of different tools aimed at the same or similar tasks by solving unit tests to study e.g. the validation, verification and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) of each model and implementation and also allow for the definition of federated workflows by clearly dividing the work of each software piece and assigning them a given computing cluster (one part in the cloud, another on-site etc.). Also automating this process or creating a demand/supply market for semi-automated execution of complex DTHs can be facilitated by advanced VHT workflow engines.

Workflow engines supporting at least version 1.2 of CWL are **cwltool**, **Arvados**, **Toil**, **StreamFlow** and **yadage**. Apart from cwltool, which is the reference implementation of the CWL standard, they all also support the **Slurm**²² (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) workload manager as execution framework.

Terra and **Seven Bridges** are commercial workflow execution engines. Terra supports WDL, whereas SevenBridges supports WDL, CWL and NFL. **Workflux** is a Python framework for platform-agnostic deployment of cwl-based workflows on workflow engines.

The organisation of use cases in containers and workflows is a clear overhead on the researchers' side and currently there are very few ways that this conversion can be leveraged. There are a myriad of different workflow managers in the biomedical domain with slightly different focuses. Some of them are open source, while others (Terra, Seven Bridges) are commercial:

Kepler, **Nextflow**, **Galaxy**, **Apache Taverna**, **cwltool**, **Cromwell**, **Snakemake**, **KNIME**, **PyCOMPSs**, **Rbbt**, **Sapporo**, **Terra**, **Seven Bridges**, ... are open-source workflow systems, which are often used in the biomedical domain.

Because of the plenitude of workflow managers, the community has been working on delivering standardised workflow descriptions such as the Common Workflow Language (CWL) and the Workflow Description Language (WDL) of Cromwell to facilitate the deployment of workflows' recipes across managers.

²⁰ https://www.commonwl.org/user_guide/

²¹ <https://github.com/openwdl/wdl>

²² <https://slurm.schedmd.com/documentation.html>

Likewise, workflows registries have been established to facilitate the discovery and re-use of scientific computational workflows in an interoperable way (**Dockstore**²³ from GA4GH and **WorkflowHub**²⁴). **Dockstore** supports CWL, WDL, NFL and Galaxy. **WorkflowHub** supports CWL, NFL, SMK, Knime and Galaxy and uses the standards RO-Crate and Bioschemas, where **RO-Crate**²⁵ is used for packaging research data objects with their metadata e.g., about the provenance information. There are also frameworks providing tools for construction and execution of workflows (e.g., the Python framework **WfCommons**²⁶) and command-line backend programs for the reproducible execution of standard CWL or NFL workflows (e.g. the Workflow Execution Service **WfEx-S**²⁷). The Workflow execution service (**WES**) API of the GA4GH provides a standardized way to submit, manage and execute workflows in different workflow languages like e.g. CWL, WDL, Nextflow, Galaxy and Snakemake.

Swift²⁸ is a programming language with workflow capabilities used for writing scripts for distributed computing. It allows the parallel execution of workflow tasks, where the data are exchanged at the begin and end of the workflow tasks.

For Galaxy workflows there is the **galaxy2cwl**²⁹ converter available and snakemake has built-in support for CWL export. For KNIME the conversion goes indirectly via defining Common Tool Descriptors (**CTD**), whereas Cromwell by default uses OpenWDL, but it also supports CWL.

Since CWL is supported by much more workflow execution engines than WDL, and a WDL to CWL converter³⁰ is available, the CWL standard should be used for describing workflows of the VHT.

2.10 Genomic sequence variants

For encoding of genomic sequence variants, one should prefer a data format mentioned in the ISO 20691 document, if applicable. An overview about sequence variation formats is given in *Table 5 in the annex*.

In molecular tumour boards and **computational oncology** such formats for sequence alignment, genome and copy number variation and DNA methylation patterns are used. These are often stored in the NCI **Cancer Research Data Commons (CRDC)**, **Genomic Data Commons (GDC)** or the **Portable Format for Bioinformatics (PFB)** format. PFB is based on the **Apache Avro** serialisation format and able to encapsulate the data model, the data dictionary, the data itself and controlled vocabularies in one file [Lukowski et al., 2023].

BioCompute objects (**BCO**) is the **IEEE 2791-2020** standard for documenting workflow steps of bioinformatics analyses of next-generation (NGS) and high-throughput screening (HTS) and is used for regulatory submissions to the FDA.

2.11 Finite element modelling (FEM)

For mesh-based **finite element modelling (FEM)**, boundary element method (**BEM**) or finite volume modelling (**FVM**) often the **.vtk** (Visualization ToolKit) output file format is used. For the FEM input files FieldML may be used. For the generation of 3D-models from DICOM data,

²³ <https://dockstore.org>

²⁴ <https://workflowhub.eu>

²⁵ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

²⁶ <https://wfcommons.org>

²⁷ <https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend>

²⁸ <http://swift-lang.org/main/>

²⁹ <https://github.com/workflowhub-eu/galaxy2cwl>

³⁰ <https://github.com/common-workflow-lab/wdl-cwl-translator>

e.g., for computer guided implant surgery, standard tessellation language (**STL**) files shall be used, which allow the printing of 3D models.

2.12 International Patient Summary (IPS)

International Patient Summary (IPS) is a set of basic patient-related physiological and clinical data and the **ISO 27269:2021**, **EN 27269:2022** and **CEN/TS 17288:2020** standard. It comprises data about medications, allergies / intolerances, problems, immunizations, results and procedures for a specified patient. It is a joint standard of five standard defining organisations (CEN, HL7, IHE, ISO and SNOMED) and actively supported by the Global Digital Health Partnership (**GDPH**) and the World Health Organisation (**WHO**). It can be implemented either by HL7 V3 Clinical Document Architecture (**CDA**), with HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (**FHIR**) or according to the Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (**IHE**) IPS profiles. Similar standards in the US are the United States Core Data for Interoperability (**USCDI**)³¹ and the Continuity of Care Record (**CCR**) defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (**ASTM**)³².

2.13 IDMP standards

The **Identification of Medicinal Products**³³ (**IDMP**) is a collection of 5 standards ensuring the safety of medications (pharmacovigilance):

- Medicinal Product Identification (**MPID**): **ISO 11615:2017**
- Pharmaceutical Product Identifier (**PhPID**): **ISO 11616:2017**
- Substance Identification (**SubID**): **ISO 11238:2018**
- Dosage Form and Route of Administration (**DF & RoA**): **ISO 11239:2012**
- Units of Measurement (**UoM**): **ISO 11240:2012**

2.14 Other data format types

If one has specific modelling requirements, then other data format types than the ones listed above are needed. Examples are **FASTQ**, a sequencing format with quality information. **SAM** (Sequence Alignment Map), **BAM** (Binary Alignment Map) and **CRAM** (Compressed Reference-oriented Alignment Map) are file **formats for alignments**.

For microscopy data **OMEX** (Open Microscopy Environment XML) is a standard for storing acquisition parameters, annotations, and image analysis results of microscopy experiments and **BDML** (Biological Dynamics Markup Language) is a standard format for storing spatiotemporal dynamics of molecules and cells in live imaging data.

For data from **wearable health devices and trackers**, e.g., weighing scales, blood pressure monitors, biosensors like blood glucose monitors, smart health watches, activity monitors, mobile ECG devices for arrhythmia recognition... the **ISO / IEEE 11073** standard for personal health devices (**PHD**) and/or **ISO/TR 14639-2:2014** for **eHealth architecture** shall be followed.

It is expected that in future also lifestyle and behavioural data from **questionnaires**, as well as registry data and **environmental data** are included in biomedical models. Standards for representing these types of data are still missing [Brunak, 2020], but the FHIR standard can in principle be adapted and used for connecting wearables to FHIR servers.

As a replacement for animal testing chemical substances shall be tested for their toxicology, e.g., in screening for adverse drug-induced arrhythmia risks. In such toxicology screenings, the pharmacodynamic **safety profiles** are reported on Safety Data Sheets (**SDS**), which are required

³¹ <https://www.healthit.gov/isa/united-states-core-data-interoperability-uscdi#uscdi-v4>

³² <https://www.astm.org/e2369-05.html>

³³ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/overview/data-medicines-iso-idmp-standards-overview>

for regulatory purposes. The content and order of the sections in such SDS are defined in the **ISO 11014:2009** standard.

For **NLP**-based modelling the NLP Interchange Format (**NIF**) shall be used.

For **clinical biomarker assays** based on mass spectrometry there is not yet a standard format available. Such a standard could be based on mass spectrometry and should combine elements from targeted **SRM** (Selected Reaction Monitoring) measurements with elements from the formats mzQC³⁴ for quality control and mzQuantML³⁵ or mzTab³⁶ for reporting quantitative measurements of the biomarkers of interest.

For standardised reporting of modelling & simulation results in pharmacometrics, the Standard Output³⁷ (**SO**) format was developed.

For radiation treatment planning the **DICOM-RT** standard is used and radiopharmaceutical therapy is regulated by the good radiopharmacy practice (**cGRPP**) guideline.

A more comprehensive and detailed listing of the recommended standards for the VHT can be found in the annex of this document and as a searchable online listing in the EDITH FAIRSharing collection at <https://fairsharing.org/4787>.

3. Standardisation of modelling

The modelling process itself shall follow the **ISO/TS 9491-1**³⁸ technical standard “*Biotechnology - Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalised medicine research - Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models*”.

For standardising the modelling process, all data, metadata, models, and simulation results shall be documented according to the **FAIR**³⁹ and **ALCOA**⁴⁰ (Attributable, Legible, Contemporaneous, Original, Accurate) principles. Therefore, one shall use standard formats with semantic annotations based on defined ontologies.

ISO/TS 9491-1 specifies requirements and recommendations for models used for research purposes in the field of personalised medicine, i.e., computational models used in routine clinical, diagnostic, or therapeutic purposes are excluded.

In detail ISO/TS 9491-1 contains specifications for:

- the design, development, and establishment of predictive computational models.
- the set-up, formatting, validation, simulation, storing and sharing of computational models.
- data used to construct or be required for validating such models.
- formatting, descriptions, annotations, interoperability, integration, access and provenance of such data.

To standardise the modelling process, the data going into a model shall be integrated and the modelling results shall be validated. The **integration** of data means the systematic combination of different data necessary for the modelling task and belonging to a patient.

³⁴ <https://hupo-psi.github.io/mzQC/>

³⁵ <https://psidev.info/mzquantml>

³⁶ <https://www.psidev.info/mztab>

³⁷ www.ddmore.foundation/our-standards

³⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/83516.html>

³⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.eurotherm.com/life-sciences-cpg/data-integrity-life-sciences/alcoa/>

The **validation** means the comparison between the output of the calibrated model and the measured data.

The **annex A of ISO/TS 9491** contains information on common standards relevant for personalised medicine and in silico approaches.

Part 2 of ISO/TS 9491 contains recommendations for implementing computational models into clinical decision support systems (**CDSS**).

3.1 Data preparation

The modelling process and the different types of models are described in detail in the **ISO/TS 9491-1**⁴¹ document “*Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models*”, that describes in detail the steps of data preparation for integrating the data into the models:

- sampling the data.
- data formatting and harmonisation, e.g., lab values shall have a unit associated with them. This unit can either be mass/volume or mol/volume. Therefore, the values shall be converted to a unique scale. For that the molecular weight of the analyte shall be known.
- data description by descriptive metadata, describing for example the context of the datasets.
- semantic annotation of the data, e.g., by annotating genes and proteins with ontology terms.
- definition of a data interoperability framework.
- data integration, either on the personal or on the variable level.
- adding data provenance information.
- defining who can access the data.

3.2 Model types

In general, one can distinguish knowledge-driven top-down models based on prior knowledge and hypotheses on the causal relationships (mechanistic models) and data-driven bottom-up models e.g., Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models.

Typical **examples for models** are:

- the risk prediction for common diseases
- disease course and therapy response prediction
- pharmacokinetic/-dynamic modelling and in silico trial simulations
- data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) models

3.3 Standards for Models

For **computer models of biological / biomedical systems** a selection of the following standards should be used.

They are often defined by community efforts like the **COMBINE**⁴² consortium and listed in detail in the **Annex A of the ISO/TS 9491-1** document “general recommendations and requirements for modelling in personalised medicine” as well as in the **Annex A and Annex B of the ISO 20691** document “*Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences*”. They are also registered in different registries like for instance the BioSimulators FAIRsharing collection⁴³, the Bio-simulation website⁴⁴ and the Normsys registry⁴⁵.

The most important standards in this category are:

⁴¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/83516.html>

⁴² <https://co.mbine.org>

⁴³ <https://fairsharing.org/1536>

⁴⁴ <https://docs.biosimulations.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://normsys.h-its.org>

- Systems Biology Markup Language (**SBML**), an XML-based description and exchange format for differential-equation models of biological processes. **Level 3** of SBML is a modular format that allows to define extension packages for other than differential-equation models.
- **CellML**, an XML-based description and exchange format for cellular models.
- **Antimony** is a modular model definition language.
- Biological Pathways eXchange (**BioPAX**) for the exchange and visualisation of biological pathway data.
- Synthetic Biology Open Language (**SBOL**) describing the exchange of synthetic biological genetic parts, devices, modules, and systems.
- Neuroscience eXtensible Markup Language (**NeuroML**) is an XML-based description and exchange format for models in neuroscience consisting of the 4 parts Biophysics, ChannelML, MorphML, and NetworkML.
- The Pharmacometrics Markup Language (**PharmML**) is an exchange format for pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic models.

A more extensive list of formats for biomedical computer models is given in *Table 6* in the annex.

For multicellular models there are currently 3 standards (MorpheusML, MultiCellDS and MultiCellML). In addition, there are several tool-specific formats, e.g. the format of the CompuCell3D tool. One should check, if one can unite these standards into one. The COMBINE consortium started already defining an **OpenVT** (virtual tissue) format for agent-based tissue modelling.

3.4 Standards for model simulations and documentation of results

For the simulation of systems biology models one of the following standard formats shall be used (see also *Table 7* in the annex). The most important standard is **SED-ML** (Simulation Experiment Description Markup Language), which is an XML-based format for encoding systems biology simulation experiments.

3.5 Standards for Graphical Model Visualisation

- KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes) Markup Language (**KGML**).
- Systems Biology Graphical Notation (**SBGN**), a graphical notation for representing biological processes.
- Systems Biology Open Language (**SBOL-Visual**) is a graphical notation to specify genetic parts, devices, modules, and systems.
- **XGMML** (eXtensible Graph Markup and Modeling Language) is a standard used for visualizing graphs like molecular interaction networks.

4. Standards for metadata of data and models

4.1 Metadata requirements

Annotation of DTHs and their parts, components and entities with metadata is a prerequisite to make models and their comprised entities FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). For integrating data from heterogeneous sources, the often-different naming of metadata attributes shall be considered. Examples of heterogeneous sources with different conventions are systems like **FHIR** (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources), **openEHR** (open Electronic Health Records), **OMOP** (Observational Medical Outcome Partnership) and **CDISC** (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium). For mapping all metadata attributes from all source formats, an intermediate convergence format (“**metadata crosswalk**”), which includes the maximum set of metadata attributes, can be used for mapping to the target format [Bönisch et al., 2022]. Recommendations on how to harmonise semantic annotations for computational models are given by [Neal et al., 2019]. Another challenge is that data fields are

often populated with values of different data types. Sometimes data fields from the input format must be splitted or merged to achieve a mapping to the target format.

The ISO 20691:2022 standard “*Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences*”⁴⁶ provides recommendations and requirements for the semantic description and annotation of data in the life sciences (including construction and validation data for computational models and DTHs). This includes a set of minimum consensus information for the annotation of biological data. Metadata and the annotation of the data integrated into DHTs should also consider domain-specific minimum information guidelines. A complete list of minimum information guidelines is given in Annex B.2 of ISO 20691:2022 “*Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences*”.

Specifically for predictive computational models in personalised medicine the ISO standard ISO/TS 9491-1 “*Biotechnology — Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalised medicine research — Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models*” comprises recommendations and requirements for the semantic description and annotation of the models and data that is integrated into them.

Metadata should consider the Minimum Information guidelines. A complete list of minimum information guidelines is given in Annex B.2 of the ISO 20691 standard. For systems biology models **MIRIAM**⁴⁷ (Minimum Information Requested in the Annotation of biochemical Models) and for simulations **MIASE**⁴⁸ (Minimum Information About a Simulation Experiment) could be relevant. **MINIMAR**⁴⁹ (Minimum Information for Medical AI Reporting) is a proposed standard for reporting of healthcare prediction models based on artificial intelligence methods.

A minimum information guideline for annotating parameter identifiability and model inference – something like a Minimal Information for Model Inference and Parametrization (**MIMIP**) - is still missing [Hucka et al. 2015]. **PETab**⁵⁰ is a format for specifying parameter estimation problems in systems biology in a tabular format.

The metadata attributes and entities should be described by using standard terminologies, controlled vocabularies, and ontologies. Such terms describe for instance the species, sex, age, organ, tissue, cell type, disease, and so on. Annotations for identifiable objects or processes, manipulated entities or used technologies are also possible. Typical metadata for modelling and simulations are terms for the used modelling parameters and the obtained simulation results.

The syntax of the semantic annotations are triplet phrases of the form “*subject – predicate – object*”. The recommended predicates are mostly ‘is’ or ‘isVersionOf’, but also other predicates are possible, see Table 1 and 2 of the ISO 20691 standard documents.

The annotation itself should be done by embedding **RDF <annotation> elements** into XML-based data files [Neal et al., 2019] but can be done also in other formats like XML or JSON, if the annotation is compatible with the W3C “Linked Open Data” concept.

For the **exchange of metadata information**, one or several of the following metadata formats/protocols should be used:

- **Investigation-Study-Assay (ISA-Tab)**, a Tab-separated format with data, model and Standard Operating Procedures (**SOPs**) stored under an ISA instance.

⁴⁶ ISO 20691: <https://www.iso.org/standard/68848.html>

⁴⁷ <http://co.mbine.org/standards/miriam>

⁴⁸ <http://co.mbine.org/standards/miase>

⁴⁹ <https://academic.oup.com/jamia/article/27/12/2011/5864179>

⁵⁰ <https://petab.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

- Investigation-Study-Assay in JSON format (**ISA-JSON**)
- Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (**FHIR**), a standard collection for semantically richly annotated healthcare data
- Health data catalogue application profile (**healthDCAT-AP**), the metadata standard of the European Health Data Space (**EHDS**).
- Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting⁵¹ (**OAI-PMH**) is a standardised protocol based on REST and XML for exchange of metadata between repositories. The REST interface contains a set of six HTTP requests or verbs (GetRecord, Identify, ListIdentifiers, ListMetadataFormats, ListRecords, ListSets) that are invoked within HTTP.
- The Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (**METS**) is an XML-based standard for encoding and exchange of metadata information. An alternative metadata format is the Extensible Metadata Platform (**XMP, ISO 16684-1:2012**).
- The protocol OAI-PMH and the metadata formats METS and XMP are candidates for the metadata schema of the EDITH catalogue. For interoperability with the EHDS, healthDCAT-AP must be supported as well.
- **odML**⁵² (Open metaData Markup Language) and **openMINDS**⁵³ are used for storing and exchanging neuroscience metadata.
- **BIDS** is used for storing imaging metadata.

“*Curation and Annotation of Logical Models*” (**CALM**) is an initiative and best practice guideline for the annotations of logical models encoded in SBML-qual [Niarakis et al., 2021].

4.2 Minimum reporting guidelines for Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS), patient-recorded outcomes and genetic risks

Part 2 of ISO/TS 9491 describes CDSSs based on AI models. **MINIMAR** (Minimum Information for Medical AI Reporting) describes the minimum set of required metadata. It also describes recommendations for clinical studies involving computational models for personalised medicine.

Other minimum reporting guidelines for a CDSS, are defined by the **EQUATOR**⁵⁴ (Enhancing the QUALity and Transparency Of health Research) network or by the **TRIPOD**⁵⁵ (Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis or Diagnosis) consortium. Other consortia defining reporting guidelines are **ISPOR** (International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research), **SMDM** (Society for Medical Decision Making) and the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (**AHRQ**).

Examples are **CONSORT** (Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials) for reporting of randomised trials, **STROBE** (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology), **SPIRIT** (Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials), a standard for trial protocols, **STARD** (STANDards for the Reporting of Diagnostic accuracy studies), **DECIDE** (Developmental and Exploratory Clinical Investigations of DEcision), **CLAIM** (Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging), **PRISMA** (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analysis) and **PROBAST** (Prediction model Risk Of Bias Assessment Tool).

There is a corresponding set of guidelines for models and trials, which are based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. These guidelines have some AI-specific items added to the checklist, e.g.

⁵¹ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

⁵² <https://www.incf.org/sbp/odml>

⁵³ <https://pypi.org/project/openMINDS/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.equator-network.org>

⁵⁵ <https://www.tripod-statement.org>

- **CHEERS-AI:** economic evaluations to estimate the cost effectiveness of AI interventions
- **CLAIM:** for medical imaging studies using AI.
- **CONSORT-AI:** for clinical trials evaluating interventions with an AI component.
- **DECIDE-AI:** for CDSSs driven by AI.
- **PRISMA-AI:** Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of AI interventions.
- **PROBAST-AI:** for prediction model studies based on AI.
- **SPIRIT-AI:** for clinical trial protocols with an AI component.
- **STARD-AI:** for reporting of diagnostic accuracy studies based on AI.
- **TRIPOD+AI:** for diagnostic or prognostic prediction models based on AI.

Part 2 of ISO/TS 9491 also describes the requirements and recommendations for **SOP's** (Standard Operating Procedures), the data collection by using the Clinical Record Forms (**CRFs**), the data cleaning, pre-processing, and post-processing steps to ensure the readiness of the data for use by the computational models and the **data analytics pipeline** with the steps study design, pre-processing, feature selection, model training and validation. Furthermore, it describes the design of integrated data repositories and the data modelling process. Important is that the black-box issue should be solved by hybrid approaches, i.e., traditional statistics combined with explainable-AI methods.

Another set of extensions is for capturing patient-recorded outcomes (**PROs**):

CONSORT-PRO Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials - PRO

SPIRIT-PRO Standard Protocol Items Recommendations for Interventional Trials - PRO

GRIPS (Genetic Risk Prediction Studies) is a guideline for the reporting of polygenic risk scores (**PRS**), **STROBE** (STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in Epidemiology) for observational epidemiological studies and **STREGA** (STrengthening the Reporting of Genetic Association studies) for genome-wide association studies.

4.3 Terminologies and ontologies for the description and annotation of data, models, and their components

Ontologies for Systems Biology / Systems Medicine / Systems Pharmacology simulation are used for the semantic annotation of algorithms and the dynamic behaviour of models.

Some ontologies are listed in the **Annex B.3 of the ISO 20691**⁵⁶ document. Others are linked by **ontology web portals** like e.g., the Open Lookup Service⁵⁷ (**OLS**), BioPortal⁵⁸, OboFoundry⁵⁹ OntoBee⁶⁰ or the semantic lookup platform⁶¹.

Ontologies typically used for in silico medicine modelling and simulation are (a more comprehensive list of ontologies is given in *Table 8* in the annex):

- Computational Neuroscience Ontology (**CNO**).
- An ontology to characterise differences in versions of computational biology Models (**COMODI**).
- Human Physiology Simulation Ontology containing concepts for simulations, models, and algorithms (**HUPSON**).
- Kinetic Simulation Algorithm Ontology for describing simulation algorithms (**KiSAO**).
- Mathematical Modelling Ontology (**MAMO**).
- Ontology of Physics for Biology (**OPB**) containing physics concepts to describe the dynamics of biological systems.

⁵⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/68848.html>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index>

⁵⁸ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org>

⁵⁹ <https://obofoundry.org>

⁶⁰ <https://ontobee.org>

⁶¹ <https://semanticlookup.zbmed.de>

- An ontology for pharmacokinetic models (**PK ontology**).
- Precision Medicine Ontology (**PreMedOnto**⁶²).
- Systems Biology Ontology (**SBO**) with terms useful for describing computational modelling.
- Terminology for the Description of Dynamics (**TEDDY**), an ontology for the description of control elements and dynamics in systems biology and synthetic biology.
- Unified Code for Units of Measure (**UCUM, ISO 11240:2012**), defined by the Regenstrief institute.
- Standardized cytopathology terminologies [Mezei, 2020]
- **ISO/IEC 20924:2024** is a vocabulary on Internet of Things (IoT) and digital twins

openMinds⁶³ (open Metadata Initiative for Neuroscience Data Structures) is a metadata framework for neuroscience graph databases defined by the Human Brain (**HBP**) and **EBRAINS** projects. It contains metadata models, libraries of controlled terminologies, brain atlases and common coordinate spaces for neuroscience graph databases. Each such metadata model consists of modular metadata schemas defining descriptions of entities from neuroscience.

4.4 Clinical languages, terminologies, and code systems

Clinical terminologies and code systems are mainly used for semantic annotation of Electronic Health Record (**EHR**) data and in FHIR⁶⁴ resources. The clinical languages like **Arden syntax** and the Clinical Quality Language (**CQL**) are both HL7 standards and allow the explicit representation of medical knowledge in Clinical Decision Support Systems (**CDSSs**) and can be used as a basis for explainability components.

The Arden syntax is built up by rule sets called Medical Logic Modules (**MLMs**), where each MLM consists of the following four categories: maintenance, library, knowledge, and resources. Each category contains slots, where the information is stored. The maintenance category contains the metadata of the MLM in slots for title, version, author, date, ... The knowledge category contains the encoded medical knowledge. [Soares et al., 2021] compares Arden syntax and CQL.

Other clinical decision support standards - also defined by HL7 - are Substitutable Medical Applications and Reusable Technology⁶⁵ (**SMART**) and **CDS Hooks**⁶⁶. SMART on FHIR provides small apps running on FHIR servers.

For the electronic Clinical Quality Measures (eCQM) used by the mentioned quality languages (Arden syntax, CQL, CDS Hooks and SMART) the Health Quality Measure Format (**HQMF**) is used.

Pharmacogenomics (**PGx**) screening can help to improve drug efficacy and reduce adverse events, but currently there is lack of pharmacogenomics (PGx) data standards for making PGx and clinical decision support systems (CDSS) interoperable [Roosan et al., 2020].

The main clinical languages and terminologies are (a more comprehensive list of clinical languages, terminologies, and code systems is given in *Table 9* in the annex; further medical vocabularies are also listed in the Unified Medical Language System (**UMLS**)⁶⁷):

- International Classification of Diseases (**ICD-11**)⁶⁸

⁶² <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/PREMEDONTO>

⁶³ <https://github.com/HumanBrainProject/openMINDS>

⁶⁴ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/resourcecelist.html>

⁶⁵ <https://smarthealthit.org>

⁶⁶ <https://cds-hooks.org>

⁶⁷ <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/sourcereleasedocs/index.html>

⁶⁸ <https://icd.org>

- Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (**LOINC**⁶⁹) for reporting laboratory test results.
- Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (**SNOMED-CT**⁷⁰).

One problem in clinical code systems is that some vary from country to country. An example is the **OPCS**⁷¹ (Classification of Interventions and Procedures) codes used in Great Britain and the **OPS**⁷² (Operationen- und Prozedurenschlüssel) Codes used in Germany. Another example are the **CPT**⁷³ (Current Procedural Terminology) and the OPS (Operationen- und Prozedurenschlüssel) codes used in Germany. A possible solution would be using a FHIR ConceptMap for mapping of the corresponding concepts.

Another problem is that there are three medical device nomenclatures (EMDN, GMDN, UMDNS). Currently there are ambitions from the WHO to define a mapping between these nomenclature systems. Since only EMDN is open source, it shall be preferentially used.

Also, for SNOMED-CT there can exist some slight differences between the national versions. One task of the so-called National Release Centers (NRCs) is to manage these national extensions, mappings, and translations.

4.5 Metadata standards, formats, and protocols

Table 10 in the annex shows an overview about general standards, formats and protocols used for metadata.

5. Model quality and validation

One prerequisite for model quality is the **quality of the used data**. Whenever possible, before processing the data, the data shall be cleaned to detect and correct inaccurate data.

The model outputs shall be **reproducible**, i.e., for non-probabilistic models, in independent runs on the same data, the model must always produce the same modelling results.

However, a general standard for model validation, independent of the model purpose, is currently still missing. On the other hand, for specific models with a well-defined purpose (e.g., in medical devices) some model quality standards are available. [Viceconti et al., 2021] propose to use an approach like the risk-based credibility assessment of ASME V&V 40 for the evaluation of new drugs.

5.1 ASME V&V 40 standard

ASME V&V 40 is a quality standard for medical devices. According to it, the model quality assessment starts with a clear definition of the scientific / medical **question of interest (QoI)** and the **context of use (CoU)**. The CoU is a complete description of the planned modelling use and defines the role and scope of the model used to address the question of interest.

In the next step the model **risk** (with its two components **model influence** and **decision consequence**) - the possibility that the results of the model simulation are wrong and lead to negative consequences for the patient - shall be assessed. The **applicability** of a model is given by the evidence to support the use of the model in the defined CoU, considering the risk.

Then a **risk-informed credibility assessment** can be performed. That credibility assessment encompasses model verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (**VVUQ**).

Model **verification (mathematical evidence)** means the confirmation that the mathematical elements of the model behave as intended and consists of two parts: code verification and simulation verification.

⁶⁹ <https://loinc.org>

⁷⁰ <https://www.snomed.org>

⁷¹ <https://digital.nhs.uk/services/terminology-and-classifications/clinical-classifications>

⁷² https://www.bfarm.de/EN/Code-systems/Classifications/OPS-ICHI/OPS/_node.html

⁷³ <https://www.ama-assn.org/amaone/cpt-current-procedural-terminology>

Model **validation (experimental evidence)** is the comparison between the modelling output of the calibrated model and the measured data, independent of the data set used for calibration, i.e., the question if the problem was solved correctly. One distinguishes between technical and clinical validation.

For **uncertainty quantification (statistical evidence)**, uncertainties on all inputs are identified and quantified, and are propagated to the simulation results to quantitatively assess the effect on the simulation results (**sensitivity coefficient method**).

Verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) for medical devices are defined in the **ASME V&V 40**⁷⁴ standard, which defines codes, standards & conformity assessment accredited also by ANSI.

Since a Virtual Human Twin (**VHT**) can be classified by a **6-dimensional framework as a backbone (x, y, z, age, credibility, clustering)**, the integration of simulation results for one patient is possible if one subsumes all results for a patient with a credibility over a given threshold and a clustering of 0 (fully personalised). The age then would be the basis for predictions over time for that patient. A clustering value of 1 would mean the whole species population.

The **credibility** is the trust in the predictive capability of the used computational model for the defined context of use. To assess the credibility of a model the verification, validation and uncertainty quantification shall be evaluated and somehow transformed into a single credibility score. Since the credibility is one axis of the 6-dimensional model of the VPH, the details of how to build such a single credibility score should be made explicit. According to ASME V&V 40 one shall assign credibility factors to each verification, validation and applicability activities. Based on that information the overall credibility can be assessed.

The Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (**CBER**) and Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (**CDER**) of the **FDA** (Food and Drug Administration) are exploring the use of the ASME V&V 40 standard for risk-informed credibility assessment in drug development⁷⁵, e.g., for the assessment of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (**PBPK**) models⁷⁶ or for Software as a Medical Device⁷⁷ (**SaMD**).

Toward Good Simulation Practice (**GSP**) of the Avicenna Alliance⁷⁸ is a regulatory guidance document with best practices for in silico trials based on computational modelling and simulation. Among others it describes the credibility and health technology assessment (**HTA**) process.

5.2 Other quality measures

For AI-based models, which learn their classification and decision rules from the data, **interpretability** of the results and **explainability** how these methods came to these results, shall be reported, as far as that is possible.

⁷⁴ <https://www.asme.org/codes-standards/find-codes-standards/v-v-40-assessing-credibility-computational-modelling-verification-validation-application-medical-devices>

⁷⁵ <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/news-events-human-drugs/promoting-innovation-medical-product-assessment-risk-based-framework-evaluating-computational-models>

⁷⁶ <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/guidance-document-on-the-characterisation-validation-and-reporting-of-physiologically-based-kinetic-models-for-regulatory-purposes.pdf>

⁷⁷ <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-software-medical-device>

⁷⁸ <https://insilico.world/community/good-simulation-practice-gsp-task-force/>

Further aspects of credibility assessment for knowledge-driven and data-driven models are described in the Avicenna Alliance white paper “*The role of artificial intelligence within in silico medicine*”⁷⁹. According to that for **closed data-driven models** (models that do not change after they have been released for use), the credibility assessment is like that of the knowledge-driven models. In contrast, **self-learning models** where every new entered data set has the potential to change the entire AI model, needs some form of a lifecycle-based regulatory framework and is currently under discussion with the FDA. A **glossary** from the Avicenna Alliance⁸⁰ with “*Terms for Computer modelling and Simulation*” is also available.

If possible, it would be desirable to further describe the trustworthiness and utilizability of models (model applicability, controllability, credibility, identifiability, explainability, interpretability, observability, transparency, repeatability, reproducibility, ...). This should also cover how a Decision Support System (DSS) comes to its decision (explainability). Such a vocabulary would help to communicate the quality of models and of simulation results based on these models. Some of the criteria (identifiability, observability) can be tested even for non-linear models e.g., by the Identifiability-Test by Radial Penalization (**ITRP**) [Kreutz, 2018] or with the Full Input-State-Parameter Observability (**FISPO**) algorithm implemented in STRIKE-GOLDD⁸¹ Matlab toolbox [Villaverde et al., 2019]. For other criteria (listed in *Table 11* in the annex) it’s hard to score them quantitatively.

The **SEPIO**⁸² (Scientific Evidence and Provenance Information Ontology) and **ECO**⁸³ (Evidence and Conclusion Ontology) can be used to represent the provenance of scientific claims and the evidence behind scientific assertions. It’s for example used in clinical genetics for representing interpretations of genetic variant pathogenicity.

Table 11 gives an overview about further data and model quality measures like e.g. reproducibility.

5.3 Validation recommendations from ISO/TS 9491-1

The ISO standard ISO/TS 9491-1 “*Biotechnology — Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalised medicine research — Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models*” defines specific recommendations for model validation of the following modelling approaches. For details see *Table 12* in the annex:

- Cellular systems biology models
- Risk prediction for common diseases
- Disease course and therapy response prediction
- Pharmacokinetic/-dynamic modelling and in silico trial simulations
- Artificial Intelligence

5.4 Quality and data security standards for medical devices

ISO 13485:2016 is a standard about quality management for medical devices to ensure that the software development life cycle steps like requirements engineering, design, risk management, testing, deployment, and maintenance are documented.

ISO/IEC 27001 describes the GDPR-compliant handling and treatment of all personal-related data with respect to cybersecurity issues.

The Medical Device Regulation (**MDR**) **EU 2017/745**, a regulation of the European Union about medical devices for human use.

⁷⁹ [https://avicenna-alliance.com/files/user_upload/PDF/AI in health - White Paper.pdf](https://avicenna-alliance.com/files/user_upload/PDF/AI_in_health_-_White_Paper.pdf)

⁸⁰ <https://avicenna-alliance.com>

⁸¹ <https://github.com/afvillaverde/strike-goldd>

⁸² <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/SEPIO-ontology>

⁸³ <https://www.evidenceontology.org>

6. Data provenance

The ISO standards **ISO/TS 23494-1**⁸⁴ and **ISO/TS 23494-2** define a Provenance information model for biological material and data.

Provenance is defined by ISO/TS 23494-1 as “information that documents the history of a described object and related described activities containing information about origin or source of the described object, any changes that may have taken place since it was originated, and who has had custody of it since it was originated”.

Whereas ISO/TS 23494-1 defines the design concepts and general requirements, ISO 23494-2 defines the **Common Provenance Model (CPM)** [Freixia, 2022] in detail. The CPM was built as an extension on top of the **W3C PROV** model. The core structure of the PROV model consists of the 3 objects **PROV-agent, PROV-activity, and PROV-entity**, which together with the relations build up the provenance graph. The idea is that domain-independent provenance information is stored in the **provenance backbone** of this graph, to which domain-specific provenance information can be attached.

In CPM the forward and backward links between provenance components in the backbone are implemented by **sender, receiver, and external input connectors**. Each of these connectors stores a PID (Persistent Identifier). This PID is for a receiver connector the identifier of the preceding chain component, for the sender connector the identifier of the following chain component and for the external input connector the identifier of the current chain component. In addition, there are 3 identifiers of meta-provenance, where the provenance information of the corresponding provenance component is stored.

If the provenance information contains sensitive or personally identifiable information, then harmonized data access agreements (hDAAs) shall be used to control data access.

PROV-O⁸⁵ is a W3C standard for a general provenance ontology and used by the common provenance model.

The **PROV-N**⁸⁶ is a notation for writing instances of the **PROV-DM**⁸⁷ data model aimed at human consumption. PROV-DM and PROV-N are described in Annexes B and C of ISO/TS 23494-2.

The **provenance information** encompasses **sample provenance** (sample collection, sample processing, transportation, sample storage) as well as **data provenance** (data generation, data processing, data validation and data retrieval). In general, each time the sample or data are somehow used or processed, the provenance information shall be updated, i.e., each step in handling the sample or data shall be documented in detail and annotated by a timestamp to finalise it.

The provenance information should be machine-readable, and the provenance information of each step should be linked together to build up an uninterrupted provenance chain, which integrates all provenance information coming from different sources. The **provenance backbone** links the inputs and outputs of an activity.

The finalised provenance information shall be regularly backed up. It is part of the metadata and shall be stored in a **FAIR** manner.

⁸⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/80715.html>

⁸⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-n/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

The finalised provenance information shall be held immutable, so that no alterations and manipulations are possible. In case of withdrawal of an informed consent, that fact shall be forwarded to any subsequent users of the sample or data.

SPIDIA⁸⁸ and SPIDIA4P are projects to standardise the pre-analytical sample-processing workflows. The **SPREC-Code**⁸⁹ (Standard PREanalytical Code) [Betsou, 2018] shall be used to encode the preanalytical treatment of biological probes and is an important part of the sample provenance information.

NIDM (NeuroImaging Data Model) defines provenance information as extensions of the **W3C-PROV** standard for human brain mapping.

An alternative method to immutably store the provenance information would be to use blockchain technology.

7. Interoperability and data quality

7.1 Data quality

Concerning the quality of the models, the **data quality** is important. Generally, the data should be checked as soon as possible. For genomics data in the **FASTQ** format, the quality is reported together with the data in the data generation process, whereas for proteomics data the quality can be stored in a separate **mzQC** file. In other cases, one shall always make use of **XML- resp. JSON schemas**, of plausibility and cross-reference checks and standardized data serialization formats. For .csv files **it always shall be defined** at which rows and columns and in which measurement unit the data fields are stored in the spreadsheet file. Sometimes **imputation** can be used to improve the data quality of data sets with **missing values**.

7.2 Serialization formats

There are two types of interoperability: technical interoperability, which includes technical interface specifications, e.g., Portable Operating System Interface (**POSIX**), and data interoperability, which is about the structure of the data and metadata and the semantics, which is important for data integration. Since technical interoperability is covered in the chapter about HPC, in the following we confine ourselves to data interoperability.

Data interoperability means to collect all the needed data coming from multiple sources and belonging together, and to make them available for further processing, analysis, and data exchange. For instance, all needed data belonging to a patient are collected and integrated for loading into one and the same model.

Such an interoperability can be reached by semantic annotation of the data with metadata and by using well-defined standard formats or data structures. Furthermore, the REST APIs should be OpenAPI⁹⁰ compliant.

In addition, whenever possible the data structures should be described by **schemas** (like e.g., XSD for XML, RDFS for RDF, JSON schema⁹¹ for JSON, YAML schema for YAML⁹² or for describing the hierarchy of HDF5⁹³, **Apache Avro** or **protobuf** formats). An overview about standard serialisation formats is shown in *Figure 1*:

⁸⁸ <https://www.spidia.eu>

⁸⁹ <https://www.isber.org/page/SPREC>

⁹⁰ <https://www.openapis.org>

⁹¹ <https://json-schema.org>

⁹² https://asdf-standard.readthedocs.io/en/1.0.3/schemas/yaml_schema.html

⁹³ https://lbann.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data_ingestion/hdf5_generate_schema_and_sample_list.html

Serialization format	Schema / IDL	Standard APIs
Apache Avro	Built-in	C, C++, C#, Java, Python, ...
FHIR	Yes	Hapi for FHIR, JSON, XML, Turtle
Java serialization	No	Yes
JSON	Partial: JSON Schema Proposal JSON-LD	Partial: Clarinet jQuery / RQL JSONPath JSON-LD
Pickle (Python)	No	Yes
Protocol Buffers (protobuf)	Built-in	C, C++, C#, Java, Python, ...
XML	XML schema RELAX NG	DOM SAX Xquery XPath

Figure 1: Standard serialisation formats (excerpt from Wikipedia)

Excel (csv) files can either be transformed into JSON format or alternatively the .csv files shall be clearly structured, i.e., shall contain headers describing the variables, their types and if necessary, also their units. **ObjTables**⁹⁴ can be used to define schemas for spreadsheet files. Another possibility is to use templates for the .csv file, e.g., defined with the **RightField**⁹⁵ [Wolstencroft et al., 2011] software, so that one can annotate the data using drop-down boxes containing the allowed ontology terms for a given spreadsheet cell.

For **text (txt) files** one shall try to represent them as either json, Avro Apache, protobuf or csv files, if that's possible. Otherwise, one shall either exactly specify the **TextFormats** [Gonnella, 2022] or one should use FHIR resources, which follow well-defined FHIR profiles against which the FHIR resources can be validated.

Further serialization formats are **HDF5** (Hierarchical Data Format) and **netCDF** (network Common Data Format). HDF is for large, complex and heterogeneous data and uses an internal file structure like a file directory structure for organizing the data. netCDF is a machine-independent format especially for array-oriented scientific data.

7.3 Clinical interoperability standards

Table 13 gives an overview about clinical interoperability standards. **BRIDG** is a standard used for interoperability of data from preclinical research, whereas **CDSIC OMOP** has its application in integration with clinical research data. **HL7 CDA** and **IHE XDS** are document interoperability standards, **DCM**'s are a set of models mainly used for integration of disease-specific data.

For interoperability of electronic health record data the standards **EEHRxF**, **FHIM**, **OpenEHR** and **FHIR** are used, i.e. beside FHIR there are several other methods which can be used for solving the interoperability problems with routine clinical data, but it's recommended to use **HL7 FHIR as standard for health data** and **healthDCAT-AP for metadata** whenever possible, since these two standards will be used by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

⁹⁴ <https://www.objtables.org>

⁹⁵ <https://rightfield.org.uk>

7.3.1 Biomedical Research Integrated Domain Group (BRIDG)

BRIDG^{96,97} is a domain model specified in UML that can bridge standards, organisations as well as the gap between clinical research and healthcare. It is also the **ISO 14199**⁹⁸ standard for biomedical and clinical research supporting semantic interoperability.

Among the stakeholders are CDISC, NCI, FDA, HL7 and ISO and the BRIDG standard is jointly balloted by ISO, HL7 and CDISC. It also defines some **BR&R** (Biomedical Research and Regulation) FHIR resources⁹⁹ like e.g., **ResearchStudy** and **ResearchSubject**. But the overall mapping and definition of FHIR resources for the BRIDG classes is very incomplete and still under way.

The BRIDG standard version 5.3.1 UML representation (defined in the BRIDG.EAP¹⁰⁰ file, developed with the **Enterprise Architect**¹⁰¹ tool) currently defines more than 300 classes in 9 subdomains (Adverse event, Biospecimen, Common, Experiment, Imaging, Molecular Biology, Protocol Representation, Statistical Analysis and StudyConduct).

Besides the UML representation, a HL7 Reference Information Model (RIM)-based representation and an ontological representation in a single OWL file are available¹⁰².

A **User's Guide**¹⁰³ is available and an **implementation guide**¹⁰⁴ is in preparation. For contributing to the BRIDG model, a **harmonisation package** with some information on how to use, to extend and to contribute to the BRIDG model, is available¹⁰⁵.

For instance, BRIDG lately incorporated classes from the **LS-DAM**¹⁰⁶ (Life Sciences Domain Analysis Model) domain model - mainly into the Experiment and MolecularBiology domain - and bridges now entities from healthcare, clinical research, and biomedical research.

On the other side some classes in the MolecularBiology domain are marked as deprecated, since it is planned to transfer them to other standardisation projects, e.g., to the **HL7 Clinical Genomics Work Group**¹⁰⁷.

Now **subdomains for modelling and simulation are missing** and still shall be defined, to allow the use of BRIDG as technology for the VHT. Inside these subdomains one could define classes like e.g., **InSilicoExperiment**, **ModelParameter**, ... that handle the different types of in silico models, their simulation, and their standard formats.

To be useful for data integration BRIDG can serve as a hub, so that different kinds of data are mapped to BRIDG and can then be translated / connected with other data without doing explicit point to point mappings between the data.

As a domain model, BRIDG can be implemented using varying technologies. One way to implement BRIDG is to map it to **FHIR**¹⁰⁸ (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) resources, which make intensive use of semantic annotation. Such FHIR resources are designed for easy data exchange and interoperability. Alternative interoperability models for implementing BRIDG would be **openEHR** (open Electronic Health Records, **ISO EN 13606**),

⁹⁶ <https://bridgmodel.nci.nih.gov/>

⁹⁷ <https://cbiit.github.io/bridg-model/HTML/BRIDG5.3.1/>

⁹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/66767.html>

⁹⁹ <https://confluence.hl7.org/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=134942425>

¹⁰⁰ <https://github.com/CBIIT/bridg-model/blob/master/Models/UML/BRIDG.EAP>

¹⁰¹ <https://sparxsystems.com>

¹⁰² <https://confluence.hl7.org/display/COD/BRIDG>

¹⁰³ https://wiki.cdisc.org/download/attachments/144549227/BRIDG_5.0_Users_Guide.pdf

¹⁰⁴ <https://bridgmodel.nci.nih.gov/bridg-implementation-guide>

¹⁰⁵ <https://bridgmodel.nci.nih.gov/download-model/harmonization-package>

¹⁰⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/1301>

¹⁰⁷ <https://build.fhir.org/genomics.html>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/resource.html>

CDISC-OMOP (Observational Medical Outcome Partnership), **VA-FHIM** (Federated Health Information Model), HL7 V3 **CDA**¹⁰⁹ (Clinical Document Architecture, an information model for text-based documents) and **DCM** (Detailed Clinical Model, **ISO 13972:2022**¹¹⁰).

An easy, extensible, and generic way to support the exchange of data files used in biological models and simulation would be to use a FHIR **Binary**¹¹¹ resource with an extension that defines the data type of the binary data by an appropriate ontology term. That even would allow the integration of other file formats (see section 3.7), for which no standardised data formats are available yet. For storing metadata, the **meta** element of the abstract base resource **Resource** can be used.

But for models in standard formats the optimal way would be to add the needed classes to a modelling and simulation subdomain of BRIDG and to define (e.g., by using the Simplifier **Forge** tool¹¹²) the needed custom FHIR resources. Then one could define a **ModelingAndSimulation** FHIR module for the BRIDG subdomain modelling and simulation, which contains the needed classes.

An example could be a class **InSilicoExperiment** derived from the Experiment class of BRIDG. Other needed classes like e.g., **BiologicalModel**, **Simulation**, **SimulationParameter**, **SimulationResult**, ... could also be defined and then the corresponding custom FHIR resources can be added to the BR&R list of BRIDG FHIR resources.

In case it's not possible to integrate a subdomain into the official BRIDG standard, one could alternatively try to establish a HL7 Computational Modeling & Simulation work group.

7.3.2 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources): ISO/AWI TR 24305

HL7 FHIR is a standard used for data exchange and/or storage of semantically annotated clinical or administrative health data and is useful for data integration and data interoperability. The standard **FHIR resources**¹¹³ - there are about 150 of them - have very generic definitions. The content of these FHIR resources can have multiple representations, e.g., as XML, JSON, UML, or RDF turtle format.

Each FHIR resource identifies itself as one of the resource types and contains:

- a uniform resource locator (URL).
- a structured data content with required and optional attributes.
- an optional identity tag with metadata, a last update timestamp and the base representation (JSON, XML, Turtle).

Some examples for FHIR resources are:

- The **Task** resource, used to launch activities and track the completion state (created, ready, in progress, stopped, terminated) of that activity. Together with the **RequestGroup** resource, which can model interdependencies between resources it can be used to implement simple workflows.
- The **Measure** and **MeasureReport** resources for defining and reporting quality measures.
- The **ResearchStudy** and **ResearchSubject** resources for clinical studies.
- The **ImagingStudy** resource represents a DICOM imaging study comprising a set of series, each of which includes a set of Service-Object Pair Instances (SOP). Each series is of only one modality (e.g., X-ray, CT, MR, ultrasound), but a study may have multiple series of different modalities.

¹⁰⁹ http://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=7

¹¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:13972:ed-1:v1:en>

¹¹¹ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/binary.html>

¹¹² <https://simplifier.net/forge>

¹¹³ <https://hl7.org/fhir/resourcelist.html>

- The **Binary** resource is very general and can be used for a general solution to exchange arbitrary data, for which there are not yet proper resources defined. Examples would be the transfer of .txt, .pdf, image or .zip files in their raw or native format. Such Binary resources can be used to integrate data files with non-standard formats (see section 3.8 Other data types).
- The **Provenance** resource describes entities and processes involved in producing or otherwise influencing a resource.

In case that no proper resource is available for the intended use, one can:

- define custom FHIR resources as a specialisation of **DomainResource**. The drawback of custom resources is that they are less interoperable.
- use the **Basic** resource and add extensions to it.
- profile already existing resources. By use of FHIR profiles and extensions one can “profile” the standard resources¹¹⁴. That means that the profiles are customised, i.e., either restricted or extended to fit one’s needs. Also, the information of base elements can be changed, or elements can be sliced. There is the **Forge**¹¹⁵ tool for defining such profiles and the profiles can be validated by different **validators**¹¹⁶ tools. Every element in a FHIR resource or data type can have an optional number of "extension" child elements. Such FHIR profiles are often used for adaptations to special national requirements.

A **FHIR profile**¹¹⁷ allows one to specify a set of constraints and/or **extensions**¹¹⁸ to define more specific resources. Every FHIR resource and every profile is defined by a **StructureDefinition**, which is a resource describing a set of data elements, extensions and constraints on resources and data types.

If one wants to search on extensions, one shall also define a corresponding **SearchParameter** resource, see the FHIR Search¹¹⁹ documentation. The **Clinical Quality Language (CQL)**¹²⁰ can be used as an alternative to FHIR search but is currently only supported by the Blaze server.

A **conformance package** contains a set of profile definitions, a manifest (based on the **Composition** resource) with the available FHIR profiles and an **implementation guide** describing these profiles. Such an implementation guide can be created with the **FHIR IG Publisher**¹²¹ or with the **ART-DECOR**¹²² tool.

FHIR can use different exchange frameworks, so that applications shall claim to be conformant with one or more of them:

- RESTful FHIR API
- FHIR messaging (message-based exchange)
- FHIR documents (document-based exchange)

A **FHIR bundle**¹²³ is a container for a collection of FHIR resources and is used for grouping resources together and transmitting them at once.

A **FHIR module**¹²⁴ is a pre-built set of FHIR resources together with pre-built flow steps that help users to access and manipulate FHIR resources in a concrete application area. An example

¹¹⁴ <https://fire.ly/blog/how-to-create-your-first-fhir-profile/>

¹¹⁵ <https://fire.ly/products/forge/>

¹¹⁶ <https://confluence.hl7.org/display/FHIR/Using+the+FHIR+Validator>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/profilelist.html>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/extensibility-registry.html>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/search.html>

¹²⁰ <https://cql.hl7.org>

¹²¹ <https://github.com/HL7/fhir-ig-publisher>

¹²² <https://art-decor.org/about-art-decor/>

¹²³ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/bundle.html>

¹²⁴ <https://hl7.org/fhir/modules.html>

is the **Diagnostic Medicine Module**¹²⁵ for requesting and reporting clinical diagnostics including laboratory testing, imaging, and genomics. An alternative module is the **genomics reporting**¹²⁶ set of FHIR resources of the clinical genomics work group, which allows the reporting of variant, pharmacogenomics, somatic and histocompatibility results.

The standard FHIR modules are:

- Conformance module
- Exchange module
- Foundation module
- Implementation Support module
- Security & Privacy module
- Terminology module
- Workflow module

7.3.2.1 FHIR terminology server

A **FHIR server** is a special type of database for storing FHIR resources. The FHIR server uses the FHIR profiles for validation of the FHIR resources. Examples for FHIR servers are the HAPI FHIR server¹²⁷, IBM LinuxForHealth¹²⁸, Blaze¹²⁹, Firely¹³⁰, MS FHIR server for Azure, Amazon HealthLake, Google cloud Healthcare, Intersystems FHIR server and Kodjin¹³¹. Unfortunately, these FHIR servers have different levels of capabilities¹³². The HAPI FHIR server is the official reference implementation of the FHIR specification and therefore supports more features than the other servers. On the other side the Blaze server shows the best performance.

For semantic annotations with terminology terms, the **Terminology resources**¹³³ shall be used. These are often stored in an own FHIR terminology server like e.g., CSIRO¹³⁴. The following terminology resources are intended for storing definitions from vocabularies / terminologies and ontologies (see figure 2):

- A **CodeSystem** is a set of concepts. Typical medical code systems are SNOMED-CT, LOINC, RxNorm, and ICD. The system element of the **Coding** data type refers to a CodeSystem resource with its basic properties (code, display, definition). An example for a Coding data would be:

```
{
  "system" : "http://loinc.org",
  "version" : "2.62",
  "code" : "55423-8",
  "display" : "Number of steps in unspecified time Pedometer"
}
```

- A **ValueSet** is a selection of a set of codes. These codes can come from one or more CodeSystems.
- A **ConceptMap** is a mapping from a set of concepts to one or more other concepts, i.e., describes the mappings between two CodeSystems.

¹²⁵ <https://hl7.org/fhir/diagnostics-module.html>

¹²⁶ <http://build.fhir.org/ig/HL7/genomics-reporting/index.html>

¹²⁷ <https://github.com/hapifhir/hapi-fhir-jpaserver-starter>

¹²⁸ <https://github.com/LinuxForHealth/fhir/releases>

¹²⁹ <https://github.com/samplify/blaze>

¹³⁰ <https://fire.ly/products/firely-server/>

¹³¹ <https://kodjin.com/kodjin-fhir-server/>

¹³² <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/capabilitystatement.html>

¹³³ <https://build.fhir.org/terminologies.html>

¹³⁴ <https://ontoserver.csiro.au/sitem>

- Whereas a CodeSystem is managed by the owner of the code system resource, a **NamingSystem** is defined by 3rd parties that use the code system. It defines the existence of a code or identifier system.
- **TerminologyCapability** defines the capabilities of a FHIR terminology server.

Figure 2: The FHIR terminology module from <https://build.fhir.org/terminology-module.html>

A **FHIR terminology service**¹³⁵ is an API or set of functions that supports e.g., the lookup, the validation and translation of codes defined by a collection of CodeSystem, ValueSet and ConceptMap resources. Besides the FHIR terminology service API the FHIR standard also defines a FHIR Search API¹³⁶.

There is a list of already known coding systems¹³⁷, which includes among others SNOMED-CT, RxNorm, LOINC and UCUM.

If one needs other terminologies, one can define them and register the OID (Object Identifier) on the HL7 OID registry¹³⁸.

In systems biology, many ontologies are defined using .obo or .owl files. The best way would be to store them in an own server independent of the clinical terminologies from where they can be loaded and parsed by OBO respective OWL file parsers.

In case one wants to store them together with the clinical terminologies on a FHIR terminology server, [Metke-Jimenez et al., 2020] describes how one can load and **transform OWL ontologies into FHIR terminology resources**¹³⁹. Because .obo files are automatically transformed to .owl by ontology portals like BioPortal or Ontology Lookup Service (OLS), it's in principle possible to transform all relevant ontology files into FHIR resources, so that they can be loaded into FHIR terminology servers like e.g. CSIRO ontoserver¹⁴⁰, the NHS terminology server¹⁴¹ or hades¹⁴². Another example is the SEMLOOKP¹⁴³ terminology service.

¹³⁵ <https://build.fhir.org/terminology-service.html>

¹³⁶ <https://build.fhir.org/search.html>

¹³⁷ <http://hl7.org/fhir/terminologies-systems.html>

¹³⁸ <http://www.hl7.org/oid/index.cfm>

¹³⁹ <https://github.com/aehrc/fhir-owl>

¹⁴⁰ <https://ontoserver.csiro.au>

¹⁴¹ <https://digital.nhs.uk/services/terminology-servers#top>

¹⁴² <https://github.com/wardle/hades>

¹⁴³ <https://semanticlookup.zbmed.de/ols/index>

Snapper¹⁴⁴ is a web-tool for creating concept maps and authoring FHIR terminology resources.

For working programmatically with FHIR there are several APIs available, e.g., the **HAPI FHIR API**¹⁴⁵ for the HAPI server. Since most FHIR servers do not support all functionality defined in the FHIR specification, their capabilities can be retrieved with the **CapabilityStatement** and **TerminologyCapability** resources.

Since the capabilities of the servers are different and/or there are also some slight differences e.g., in the search behaviour, each FHIR server has its own API.

7.3.3 OpenEHR (*Open Electronic Health Records*)

An alternative to FHIR is openEHR¹⁴⁶, an open health interoperability standard standardised by the ISO 13606 series, which is patient-centric, i.e., all health data for a person are stored in a lifetime, vendor-independent EHR for that patient. It's described in the white paper¹⁴⁷.

openEHR contains abstract specifications, the Platform independent Model (**PIM**) - some of them specified as Antlr grammars - and the Implementation Technology Specifications (**ITSs**) or Platform-Specific Models (**PSMs**), which comprise JSON and XML schemas, **BMM** (Basic Meta-Models) and REST-APIs.

The PIM allows easy adaptations to change to new information technologies and defines the abstract and stable **Reference Information Model (RIM)**, which is equal for all openEHR systems. That means that the RIM is followed by each openEHR implementation. The RIM was **defined by domain experts (clinicians)** independent of any implementation restrictions, i.e., it is a pure logical model. It is implemented by archetypes and templates in the PSM. The **archetypes** (possible data points / data groups) for the archetype object model (**AOM**) are written in **ADL** (Archetype Definition Language). The Clinical Knowledge Manager¹⁴⁸ (**CKM**) is a library of openEHR archetypes.

A **template** is an aggregation (tree) of archetypes, where each archetype constrains instances of various RIM types. Then things like e.g., XSDs, API facades, REST APIs/URIs, UI forms, schemas, message definition... are **generated** by tools from these templates, i.e., no further manual intervention is involved in this step. The REST APIs are for example generated by the tool **EhrScape**¹⁴⁹. There is also a web site with an overview about other openEHR modelling tools¹⁵⁰, like e.g., the **ADL Workbench**, the **ArchetypeDesigner** and the **TemplateDesigner**. The logic of decision support systems can be expressed by the Guideline Definition Language (**GDL**)¹⁵¹.

Beside the RIM there is a supporting terminology specification¹⁵² (**TERM**) defining the used vocabulary and code sets.

By using archetype profiles one can constrain classes from the generic archetypes in order to define custom archetypes. For searching and retrieving data from the archetype repository there is the archetype query language (**AQL**). AQL-Queries are portable since they rely on logical content definitions and depend not on physical database schemas.

The archetypes in openEHR are somewhat comparable to the resources in FHIR, but in contrast to FHIR the focus is not so much on data exchange, but on semantic domain modelling.

¹⁴⁴ <https://ontoserver.csiro.au/site/our-solutions/snapper/>

¹⁴⁵ <https://hapifhir.io>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.openehr.org>

¹⁴⁷ https://www.openehr.org/resources/white_paper_docs/openEHR_vendor_independent_platform.pdf

¹⁴⁸ <https://ckm.openehr.org/ckm/>

¹⁴⁹ <https://dev.ehrscape.com>

¹⁵⁰ https://www.openehr.org/products_tools/modelling_tools/

¹⁵¹ <https://specifications.openehr.org/releases/CDS/latest/GDL.html>

¹⁵² <https://specifications.openehr.org/releases/TERM/latest/SupportTerminology.html>

One big difference is that openEHR is based on logical modelling, whereas FHIR is much more implementation dependent, and the information representation is much more fragmented. This has the consequence that for each data point a lot of context information is retrieved, so that the total number of queries is much higher, and the databases and applications are less maintainable. In openEHR this information would be already contained in the templates.

Another disadvantage of FHIR is that it has its own content model and requires a mapping of the existing clinical data model to the FHIR resource profiles (often containing extensions and slices), which can be both costly and error prone.

7.3.4 CDISC OMOP (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership)

CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) is a consortium, which defines several open standards for regulatory approval and case report forms, e.g.

ADaM Analysis Data Model for data and metadata of clinical trial statistical analysis

CTR-XML Clinical Trial Registry-XML

ODM-XML Operational Data Model-XML

OMOP Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership

SDTM Study Data Tabulation Model for clinical study data in a tabular format

The OMOP Common Data Model (**CDM**) is an open community standard for observational health data. It uses the **OHDSI**¹⁵³ (Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics) **standard vocabularies**¹⁵⁴.

The OMOP concept is to transform data into CDM format with a common semantic representation by using terminologies, vocabularies, and coding schemes.

OMOP-CDM offers **standardised analytical tools**, e.g., for data quality and characterization, medical product safety surveillance, comparative effectiveness, quality of care, and patient-level predictive modelling. Therefore, for performing analyses one can do one of the following:

- use the interactive analysis platform **ATLAS**¹⁵⁵.
- write code that uses the R packages of the OHDSI methods library.
- write custom code.

Whereas FHIR uses resources and openEHR archetypes / templates, in OMOP CDM all clinical events like conditions, procedures, drug exposures... are stored in **concepts**.

OMOP is mainly suited for research purposes (clinical studies).

7.3.5 HL7 V3 CDA (Clinical Document Architecture)

CDA is built on HL7 version 3 and is an abstract information model that can be seen as a predecessor of FHIR. By Implementation Technology Specifications (**ITs**) it is described how the model can be implemented, e.g., by XML-based documents. An important tool for creation of CDA templates and value sets is **ART-DECOR**¹⁵⁶. The ART-DECOR tool is also a repository for the reuse of CDA-templates and can also be used for the definition of FHIR profiles.

7.3.6 IHE Cross-Enterprise Document Sharing (XDS)

XDS¹⁵⁷ is a **IHE** (Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise) integration profile for sharing of documents between healthcare enterprises.

¹⁵³ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/>

¹⁵⁴ <https://github.com/OHDSI/Vocabulary-v5.0/releases>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.ohdsi.org/software-tools/>

¹⁵⁶ <https://art-decor.org>

¹⁵⁷ <https://profiles.ihe.net/ITI/TF/Volume1/ch-10.html>

7.3.7 Federated Health Information Model (FHIM)

VA-FHIM¹⁵⁸ is a further UML-based logical health information model defined by the Open Group, intended to achieve interoperability. It is specified in UML and comprises 42 domains, with in total over 1000 classes. FHIM can be used to translate and transform between multiple standards and protocols. For example, FHIM does also support transformation into HL7 FHIR. FHIM provides its own **Profile Builder**¹⁵⁹ tool.

7.3.8 Clinical Information Modelling Initiative (CIMI)

CIMI (<http://models.opencimi.org/cimi>) is a reference model initiative under the roof of HL7 that defines common formats for health information with the goal of improving the interoperability between the different healthcare systems.

7.3.9 Detailed Clinical Model (DCM)

DCM is the **ISO 13972:2022** standard. It defines data elements, the relationships between such data elements and terminologies for detailed small, reusable clinical models. It's an abstract standard which can in principle be implemented in different ways, e.g., by use of FHIR, openEHR, CDA, OMOP.

7.3.10 European Electronic Health Record eXchange Format (EEHRxF)

In the future, the **European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format**¹⁶⁰ (EEHRxF) is recommended by the European Commission to be used as framework for the exchange of Electronic Health Record data. It can be implemented using FHIR, IHE or OpenEHR profiles.

As a conclusion it can be stated that for modelling on the semantic level BRIDG, FHIM and DCM are ideally suited, whereas for a concrete technical implementation CDA, FHIR, openEHR and OMOP are the proper standards.

7.3.11 Integration of and examples for multiscale models

Some challenges in multiscale modelling are discussed by [Fletcher, Osborne, 2021].

7.3.11.1 Technical integration aspects

Multiscale models have model features at multiple scales of space and/or time. The Multiscale Modelling and Simulation Framework (MMSF) was defined by [Borgdorff et al., 2013] and [Chopard et al., 2014]. It is based on the Multiscale Modelling and Simulation Language (MMSL) [Veen, Hoekstra, 2020], which describes the coupling of many sub-models to the multiscale model by using **MUSCLE3** (Multiscale Coupling Library and Environment).

One proposal is to integrate machine learning and multiscale modelling [Alber et al., 2019], where machine learning explores big parameter spaces for the identification of correlations and the multiscale modelling predicts the system dynamics and identifies causality. In such a combined model's system validation is of prime importance to avoid that the ML algorithm leads to non-physical resp. non-biological solutions.

Prospectively, markup-languages permitting a unique description of models should describe all mechanistic models, including even agent-based models of individual cells that are becoming increasingly sophisticated. **Agent-based models** based on MultiCellDS or MultiCellML allow the integration to intercellular spatial models and may be promising steps into this direction.

Tightly coupled multiscale models, where models interact in cycles (e.g. a microscale model providing input data to a macroscale model, that in turn at the next time step provides input data

¹⁵⁸ <https://fhim.org/fhim-model>

¹⁵⁹ https://fhim.org/fpb_download

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.x-ehealth.eu/eehrxf>

the microscale model, etc.) require dedicated coupling frameworks, as discussed above, and from the point of view of the VHT they are considered a new model.

In contrast, **loosely coupled multiscale models** do not have such cyclic feedback loops and can be composed as a workflow and are therefore viewed as a workflow resource.

7.3.11.2 Biological integration aspects

An example for a multiscale model is the integration of cell-based models to **tissue- or organ-based models**, for instance by exploiting knowledge about intercellular signalling processes, e.g., from the **OmniPath**¹⁶¹ database.

Another example is the **whole-body** metabolism (**WBM**) model [Thiele et al., 2020] that can predict inter-organ metabolic cycles (**Cori** and **Cahill cycle**) based on information from literature and measured -omics data. It uses and integrates molecular-level, organ-specific (from the virtual metabolic human (**VMH**, www.vmh.life)) and sex-specific genome-scale metabolic reconstructions of 26 organs, six blood cell types and 13 biofluid compartments and integrates its host-microbe co-metabolism.

A further example would be the integration of system-wide acting molecules, like neurotransmitters, hormones or immune cells and immune factors, with cell-, tissue- or organ-level models.

Other examples are whole-body pharmacokinetic models, where the integration of pharmacodynamic drug actions with drug distribution in deep compartments is possible.

8. Phenotypic data exchange

Phenopackets¹⁶² version 2 is a Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (**GA4GH**) and **ISO 4454**¹⁶³ open standard for sharing disease and phenotype information of a patient/sample, especially in the context of diseases, especially for rare diseases, cancer, but also for common diseases. A Phenopacket links detailed phenotypic descriptions with disease, patient, and genetic information, diagnosis, and treatments.

The phenotypic features are e.g., signs, symptoms, laboratory and imaging findings, behavioural manifestations, or the results of physiological tests.

The **Human Phenotype Ontology**¹⁶⁴ (**HPO**) and other disease ontologies like e.g., **Mondo**, **OMIM** (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man), **ORDO** (Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology), **NCIT** (National Cancer Institute Thesaurus), **ICD** (International Classification of Diseases) etc. contain many terms describing phenotypic abnormalities. Mondo tries to harmonise the different disease definitions and is coordinated with HPO.

Therefore, Mondo should be the preferred source for disease definitions and HPO should be used for describing the phenotypic features constituting this disease.

The Phenopackets **schema**¹⁶⁵ defines the building blocks of a Phenopacket. The three top-level building blocks are **Phenopacket**, **Cohort** and **Family**. Each top-level building block shall contain a **MetaData** block containing the metadata.

¹⁶¹ <https://omnipathdb.org>

¹⁶² <http://phenopackets.org>

¹⁶³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79991.html>

¹⁶⁴ <https://hpo.jax.org/app/>

¹⁶⁵ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

The building blocks can be combined to create larger blocks. Each Phenopacket can contain a list of **PhenotypicFeature**¹⁶⁶ elements, where each PhenotypicFeature is defined by an ontology term, which can be present or absent (excluded), and is described further by information like the severity, modifiers, disease onset and resolution.

The Phenopackets schema is specified as a **protobuf schema**¹⁶⁷. These protocol buffers are platform- and language-neutral, so that serialisation code for several programming languages can be generated easily. Therefore, Phenopackets is a standard for the language- and platform-neutral exchange of phenotypic information.

It is planned to integrate the Phenopackets with FHIR¹⁶⁸. For that a Phenopackets on FHIR¹⁶⁹ implementation guide¹⁷⁰ is available.

9. Standardised bundling of data for individuals / patients

For healthcare applications the data integration has often to be done for the individual patients. Such **data integration** on the level of individuals means to integrate all data types from a patient into a collection of data that can be used to support model-building and to conduct simulation with that data collection for that patient. This allows one to build and simulate personalised medicine models.

Such an **integration on the patient level** requires that the data protection laws, especially the **EU-GDPR** (General Data Protection Regulation) are regarded. The patient has to give his informed consent or the national data protection laws shall be followed. Without consent the data are not allowed to contain personally identifiable information.

If consent is given, the Data Use Ontology (**DUO**) contains standardised terms for documenting the consented data uses. In case no consent is given, one can at first bundle the data of that patient and then anonymize them. If that's not possible one shall use pseudonymised data and then bring the data of one patient together. For that, the pseudonymisation method shall be the same for all data sources.

A special problem is **record linkage**, where different data sets from a patient (who potentially was treated in more than one clinic) should be linked together across organisations or even countries. This is for example necessary to get large enough case numbers for the analysis of rare diseases with data-driven AI or ML methods. For that one needs a method to link datasets of a patient from more than one organisation without making reidentification of the patients possible.

The outcome of such **Privacy Preserving Record Linkage**¹⁷¹ (**PPRL**) algorithms depend on the configuration of several algorithm parameters. Therefore, if two organisations want to filter datasets based on Bloom filters, they use the same set of parameters for the Bloom filter generation.

One possibility to tackle that problem would be to use such PPRL with Bloom-filters [Schnell, Borgs 2017], which have the disadvantage that a low rate of false positives is possible. According to [Randall 2022] 99.3% of groupings are identical between privacy preserving and clear-text linkage. It's still an open question if methods based on asymmetric key cryptography behave better.

¹⁶⁶ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/phenotype.html>

¹⁶⁷ <https://developers.google.com/protocol-buffers>

¹⁶⁸ <https://confluence.hl7.org/display/VA/Vulcan+Phenopackets>

¹⁶⁹ <https://github.com/phenopackets/phenopacket-schema-fhir-implementation-guide>

¹⁷⁰ <http://phenopackets.org/core-ig/>

¹⁷¹ <https://www.boozallen.com/insights/ai/privacy-preserving-record-linkage.html>

9.1 Privacy-preserving distributed computation

Another possibility to follow the data protection laws is to use **SMPC (Secure Multi-Party Computation)** techniques for the analysis. In SMPC techniques the data are kept private on the distributed computation nodes and only partial results are shared without revealing any original data. Then, from the partial results the global result can be computed. Examples are e.g., **EasySMPC**¹⁷² or federated secure computing (**fdrtd**¹⁷³).

Other possibilities let remain the sensitive data where they are stored: **DataSHIELD**¹⁷⁴ in combination with the data management application **OPAL**¹⁷⁵ (“bring the analysis to the data”), whereas the **Personal Health Train**¹⁷⁶ (PHT) uses data from various sources in decentralised databases.

Fed-BioMed¹⁷⁷ is another framework for federated learning with decentralized data.

10. Other aspects (life cycle management, benchmarking, risk management)

- For **life-cycle management** and **versioning** of models the **PAV** ontology, which is a specialization of W3C-PROV-O, shall be used. For life-cycle management of data belonging to a patient the patient-centred CDS framework proposed by [Sittig *et al.*, 2023] can be used. It consists of 8 stages in three phases (healthcare delivery phase, knowledge generation phase and clinical decision support phase) and is based on patient-centred outcomes research (**PCOR**).

The document “The Software Precertification (Pre-Cert) Pilot Program: Tailored Total Product Lifecycle Approaches and Key Findings” [FDA, September 2022] describes a Total Product Lifecycle (**TPLC**) perspective for AI/ML-based models following the GMLP (Good Machine Learning Practices) guidelines.

- For **benchmarking** of models, for comparison one needs gold standards like e.g. performance metrics and/or standardized test models [Mangul *et al.*, 2019].
- **Risk management** is implicitly handled by the risk-based credibility assessment procedure building upon ASME V&V-40, where the model risk matrix is described by the two factors model influence and decision consequence. In addition, there is the **ICH guideline Q9**¹⁷⁸ on quality risk management, which describes the risk management process with its components risk assessment, risk control, risk review and risk communication and some risk management methods. Relevant standards for risk management are:
 - **ISO 14971:2019** Medical devices—Application of risk management to medical devices
 - **IEC 80001-1:2021** Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices—Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software

11. Missing standards still under development

Some desirable standards are still lacking, and the time frame of the EDITH project is too short for the full definition of needed new standards, but we started already the definition process for the following standardization projects:

¹⁷² <https://github.com/easy-smpc/easy-smpc>

¹⁷³ <https://github.com/federatedsecure>

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.obiba.org/pages/products/datashield/>

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.obiba.org/pages/products/opal/>

¹⁷⁶ www.health-ri.nl/initiatives/personal-health-train

¹⁷⁷ <https://fedbiomed.gitlabpages.inria.fr>

¹⁷⁸ https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/international-conference-harmonisation-technical-requirements-registration-pharmaceuticals-human-use-ich-guideline-q9-quality-risk-management-step-5-first-version_en.pdf

- **Adaptation of ASME V&V-40:2018 standard:** The goal is the adaptation of the ASME V&V-40 medical device standard for the risk-informed credibility assessment of biochemical models (SaMD). The new standard should include the assessment of agent-based models (AGM's) as well as data-driven (AI/ML) models. We have already established a joint IEC TC 62 / ISO TC 276 working group.
- **Standardization for agent-based modeling: openVT (Virtual Tissue):** The goal is to develop a multi-scale agent-based standard with abstract concepts (“objects”, “processes”, “connections”), which subsumes the current MorpheusML, MultiCellDS, MultiCell3D standards and the proprietary CompuCell3D format. It is planned to also define a proper uniform terminology and that the new standard supports the SBML, Antimony, CellML, MaBoSS and the BioNetGen network standards. This standard is currently under discussion in the COMBINE network.
- **Development of a new workflow standard for the VHT's** as decided in the break-out session of the Paris meeting. Until now no official definition group was established, since it should first be analyzed and made explicit, which features and concepts are missing in the current CWL (Common Workflow Language) standard and what are the expected additional features from the new standard.
- **Standard for the semantic description of virtual twins in healthcare:** There are already plenty of official standards from ISO, IEC, IEEE, ITU and W3C available describing in detail the technology of important components and parts (virtual entities, physical entities, data, connection, services, sensors, ...) of technical digital twins¹⁷⁹, but the overall architecture of a digital twin solutions is still under debate and keeps going. In addition, there are the DTDL¹⁸⁰ (Digital Twin Definition Language) defined by Microsoft and the W3C Web of Things¹⁸¹ (WoT) standard. For digital twins in healthcare, one needs a specific standard for their semantic description. Such a standard is currently under discussion in the COMBINE network and comprises several levels of metadata (biological, technical, legal and descriptive metadata) describing a VHT:

Biological metadata:

- organism (human for the VHT)
- domain of model (medical, epidemiological, behavioral, ecological, populational)
- sort of model (ensemble model, single model)
- model types (physiological / pathophysiological, biomechanical, imaging, systems biology / systems medicine / systems pharmacology / systems toxicology)
- purpose (research, monitoring, diagnostic, prognostic, therapy choice, therapy optimization, risk prediction, education, biomanufacturing, healthcare/hospital management)
- system level (molecular, pathways, subcellular, cell, tissue, organ, organ system, whole body, communities (epidemiological or population statistical models))
- biological integration into multiscale models (cell-cell signaling (tissue factors), nervous signals, hormones, microbiome interactions (skin, gut), PBPK (Physiology-Based Pharmacokinetic model))
- information/data basis of model (mechanistic model, data-based (statistical) model, AI/ML model, hybrid model, agent-based model)
- target value of prediction (scale value, survival time, yes/no, risk, recommendation)

Technical metadata:

¹⁷⁹ <https://digitaltwin1.org/articles/2-4>

¹⁸⁰ <https://azure.github.io/opendigitaltwins-dtdl/DTDL/v3/DTDL.v3.html>

¹⁸¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/wot-thing-description11>

- components of a DT (data, model or ensemble of models, **comparator**: divergence between the predicted state and observed state, **actuator**: does something in response to comparator output, **control**: decision what to do, i.e., model reacts to events)
- DT interface: input and output data (data type, data format, frequency of data acquisition, availability, reliability, security, units)
- required runtime parameters (significance level, ...)
- parametric variability (how to adapt a generic model to become an individual, i.e. a personalized digital twin)
- “Parameter cloud” within which the model functions correctly
- technical integration into multi-scale/multi-organ models (VHT as a collection of DTHs): modularization → need for internal interfaces and a modularized architecture
- model validation (ASME V&V 40, identifiability, observability, reproducibility, explainability, controllability). Problem for personalized models: validation can only be done retrospectively!
- language runtime (C, CLR, JRE, R, Julia, Jupyter, Mathematica, Matlab/GNU Octave, Python)
- runtime dependencies (libraries, operating system)
- execution hardware (workstation, HPC cluster, cloud, quantum)
- execution environment (containerized, Workflow Execution Service (WfExS), web application running in the browser, command-line)
- container type (Docker, Apptainer)
- execution / solver software (COPASI, libroadrunner, Morpheus, Tellurium, Vivarium, XPPAUT)
- model type (ABM, algebraic equations, Bayesian, Boolean, Graphical, linear equations, metabolic network, ODE, PDE, Petri, stoichiometric)
- model format (CellML, FieldML, SBML, R, XPP)
- data serialization format (XML, RDF, JSON, JSON-LD, YAML, FHIR, Apache Avro, Google protobuf) for patient / healthcare data files
- credibility (0.00: no credibility assessment done, ... 1.00: certified by regulatory agency)
- clustering (0: individual-level, ... 1: population-level)

Legal metadata:

- privacy / data protection issues (anonymization, pseudonymization, consent, GDPR)
- data security
- data encryption
- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
- license information: list from the Open Software Initiative (OSI) or Software Package Data Exchange (SPDX)

Descriptive metadata:

- title of the digital twin
- description of the digital twin
- targeted group (age, sex, other inclusion/exclusion criteria)
- regulatory aspects (approval by FDA and/or EMEA; “approval number”)
- links (to publication, documentation website, source code)
- version
- last update date
- funding
- authors

12. Needs and gaps analysis / Open questions

- Formal standards are more binding than community standards. Therefore, one should develop the community standards further into formal standards, if possible.
- Can SED-ML be used as THE defined reference standard for EDITH to transfer the simulation description?
- There are several options for the interoperability problem. Some possible interoperability frameworks are FHIR, openEHR, CDISC-OMOP, VA-FHIM, ... Which one should be used?
- Solve the problem of data integration and interoperability with preclinical, clinical and translational research data based on BRIDG: extending BRIDG by adding subdomains for modelling and simulation with the needed classes and define the corresponding FHIR resources.
- How can the integration of multiscale models be tackled in general? Can such a general multiscale standard be developed, e.g. based on existing digital twin frameworks / architectures [Agmon et al., 2022, Masison et al., 2021, De Benedictis et al., 2022], multiscale modelling frameworks [Chopard 2014] and the Multiscale Modeling and Simulation Language (MMSL)?
- How to integrate models on different scales (cell, tissue, organ, whole body) into a whole-body model? Is MMSL enough for that? Such modularized models comprising different modelling approaches need a standardised exchange format on the meta-level.
- Develop harmonised Data Access Agreements (hDAAs) for the access to personal data (and the models derived from that data).
- There are no standards for lifestyle and environmental data.
- There are no standards for radiation and radiopharmaceutical therapy.
- There is no standard for clinical biomarker assays.
- There are no standards to integrate pharmacogenomics (PGx) data with CDSSs.
- There is no standard for multicellular tissue modelling.
- A standard for Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) is still missing.
- A standard for assessing the **quality of data** is missing.
- A standard for access to data for model validation + instantiation (adaption to the patient) is needed.
- Clear standards on how to semantically annotate the different types of models (e.g., RDF <annotation> elements for XML-based files, ...) are needed.
- Should a vocabulary describing the trustworthiness and utilizability of systems models (model applicability, controllability, credibility, identifiability, explainability, interpretability, observability, transparency, repeatability, reproducibility, ...) be used for reporting further aspects of model quality?
- Can the SEPIO ontology be used for reporting the evidence of scientific claims resulting from the models [Viceconti et al., 2021]?
- A standard for describing the needed runtime environment requirements, e.g., operating system, HPC, Docker/Apptainer (former Singularity), need of WSL-2 (Windows Subsystem for Linux), ... is still missing. Can the Runtime Requirements Ontology (**RRO**) be used for that?
- The problem of Privacy Preserving Record Linkage (**PPRL**) is not yet generally solved, since a small rate of false positives is possible and personalised data encoded with Bloom filters can be re-identified with ML techniques. Do methods based on asymmetric key cryptography behave better?
- There are many standards for electro- and neurophysiology, biosignal and vital sign data, which all encode similar data. Is it possible to develop one overarching standard, which unites the capabilities of these standards?
- A general standard for reporting the simulation output data - like the Standardized Output (**SO**) standard in pharmacometrics - is still missing.

- Can the MultiCellML, MultiCellDS and MorpheusML standards be united into one overarching standard?
- There is a standardized digital twin framework for manufacturing (**ISO 23247:2021**) already available. Can this adapted to be useful for healthcare digital twins, which have some special requirements (e.g., privacy and security of data, due to personalization the validation can only be done retrospectively, ...)?
- The COMBINE consortium started to develop a “Standard for Digital Twins of Living Systems” for the semantic description of digital twins in the life sciences encompassing descriptive, technical, biological and legal metadata describing a virtual twin.

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Annex

The EDITH standards collection at <https://fairsharing.org/4787> contains the standards mentioned in tables 3 until 9 and will be kept up to date.

Tables

Table 1: Technical standard defining organisations

Standard defining organisation	Description
ASME ¹⁸²	American Society of Mechanical Engineers Defines codes and standards for mechanical engineering. Important subcommittees are: VVUQ SC 40 Computational Modelling of Medical Devices VVUQ SC 60 Guideline for Simulation Software Selection VVUQ SC 70 Machine Learning Applied to Mechanistic & Process Modelling
ASTM ¹⁸³	American Society for Testing and Materials
Avicenna Alliance ¹⁸⁴	An international alliance with the goal of making <i>in silico</i> medicine a standard practice in healthcare. The Toward Good Simulation Practice (GSP) book issued by the alliance is intended as a quality standard for in silico clinical trials by assuring the credibility of in silico models.
CEN / CENELEC ¹⁸⁵	European Committee for Standardization The CEN Technical Committee CEN/TC 251 defines standards for health informatics
COMBINE ¹⁸⁶	Computational modelling in Biology Network. Coordinates the development of community standard formats for systems biology modelling.
DICOM ¹⁸⁷	Digital Medicine and Communications in Medicine DICOM is a standard for medical imaging data (ISO 12052:2017).
GA4GH ¹⁸⁸	Genome Alliance for Genomics and Health Standards for collecting, storing, analysing, and sharing of genomic data within research and healthcare
HL7 ¹⁸⁹	Health Level 7 (since it is located on the highest level 7, the application layer, of the ISO/OSI communication model) Defined a set of standards for the exchange of electronic clinical and health administrative information
IEC ¹⁹⁰	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE ¹⁹¹	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO/TC 215 ¹⁹²	International Standards organisation (ISO) Technical Committee 215 Standardisation in the field of health and medical informatics

¹⁸² <https://www.asme.org/codes-standards>

¹⁸³ <https://www.astm.org>

¹⁸⁴ <https://avicenna-alliance.com/>

¹⁸⁵ <https://standards.cenelec.eu>

¹⁸⁶ <http://combine.org>

¹⁸⁷ <https://www.dicomstandard.org>

¹⁸⁸ <https://www.ga4gh.org>

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.hl7.org>

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.iec.ch/homepage>

¹⁹¹ <https://standards.ieee.org>

¹⁹² <https://www.iso.org/committee/54960.html>

ISO/TC 276/WG5 ¹⁹³	International Standards organisation (ISO) Technical Committee 276 (meta)data standards for the life sciences and for data processing
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Table 2: Clinical standard defining organisations

Standard defining organisation	Description
CDISC ¹⁹⁴	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium Definition of several standards for clinical trials and case report forms (e.g., ADaM, CTR-XML, ODM-XML, OMOP, SDTM)
C-Path ¹⁹⁵	Critical Path Institute
DDMoRe ¹⁹⁶	Drug Disease Model Resources (DDMoRe) Foundation
ECRI ¹⁹⁷	Emergency Care Research Institute
ICH ¹⁹⁸	International Council for Harmonisation
ICHOM ¹⁹⁹	Standards organisation for patient outcomes
IDMP ²⁰⁰	Identification of Medicinal Products
IHE ²⁰¹	Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise is an industry initiative to improve healthcare information sharing. It is organised into domains addressing specific healthcare areas. The IHE integration profiles specify how to use existing standards.
IHTSDO ²⁰²	International Health Terminology Standards Development Organization, the organisation defining the SNOMED-CT ²⁰³ (Systematised Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms) terms
INCF ²⁰⁴	International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility, which develops standards for neuroscience
JIC ²⁰⁵	Joint Initiative Council - Initiates joint initiatives of nine major SDO's in health informatics standardisation
ISoP ²⁰⁶	International Society of Pharmacometrics - Data Standards Working Group
NCI-EVS ²⁰⁷	National Cancer Institute - Enterprise Vocabulary Service
OHDSI ²⁰⁸	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
Regenstrief ²⁰⁹	The Regenstrief institute defines the LOINC and UCUM codes
TransCelerate ²¹⁰	TransCelerate Clinical Data Standards Initiative
WHO ²¹¹	World Health Organization

¹⁹³ <https://www.iso.org/committee/4514241.html>¹⁹⁴ <https://www.cdisc.org/standards>¹⁹⁵ <https://c-path.org/news-and-events/data-standards/>¹⁹⁶ <https://www.ddmore.foundation>¹⁹⁷ <https://home.ecri.org>¹⁹⁸ <https://www.ich.org/page/ich-guidelines>¹⁹⁹ <https://www.ichom.org>²⁰⁰ www.fda.gov/industry/fda-data-standards-advisory-board/identification-medicinal-products-idmp²⁰¹ <https://www.ihe.net>²⁰² <https://confluence.ihtsdotools.org>²⁰³ <https://www.snomed.org>²⁰⁴ <https://www.incf.org>²⁰⁵ <http://www.jointinitiativecouncil.org>²⁰⁶ <https://go-isop.org/committees/standards-best-practices-committee/data-standards-working-group/>²⁰⁷ <https://evs.nci.nih.gov>²⁰⁸ <https://www.ohdsi.org>²⁰⁹ <https://www.regenstrief.org>²¹⁰ <https://www.transceleratebiopharmainc.com/initiatives/clinical-data-standards/>²¹¹ <https://www.who.int>

Table 3: Standards for medical imaging

Medical imaging standard	Description																		
BIDS ²¹²	Brain Imaging Data Structure, a standard of the INCF ²¹³ (International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility) for capturing data and metadata of MRI datasets. For different imaging techniques the following extensions ²¹⁴ to BIDS are available: <table border="1" data-bbox="507 524 1382 943"> <tr> <td>ASL-BIDS</td> <td>- for arterial spin labelling</td> </tr> <tr> <td>EEG-BIDS</td> <td>- for electroencephalographic data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>iEEG-BIDS</td> <td>- for intracranial EEG data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>fNIRS-BIDS</td> <td>- for Near InfraRed Spectroscopy</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Genetics-BIDS</td> <td>- for genetic data associated with human brain imaging</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MEG-BIDS</td> <td>- for magnetoencephalographic data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Microscopy-BIDS</td> <td>- for microscopy imaging data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PET-BIDS</td> <td>- for positron emission tomography</td> </tr> <tr> <td>qMRI-BIDS</td> <td>- for quantitative MRI data</td> </tr> </table>	ASL-BIDS	- for arterial spin labelling	EEG-BIDS	- for electroencephalographic data	iEEG-BIDS	- for intracranial EEG data	fNIRS-BIDS	- for Near InfraRed Spectroscopy	Genetics-BIDS	- for genetic data associated with human brain imaging	MEG-BIDS	- for magnetoencephalographic data	Microscopy-BIDS	- for microscopy imaging data	PET-BIDS	- for positron emission tomography	qMRI-BIDS	- for quantitative MRI data
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fNIRS-BIDS	- for Near InfraRed Spectroscopy																		
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MEG-BIDS	- for magnetoencephalographic data																		
Microscopy-BIDS	- for microscopy imaging data																		
PET-BIDS	- for positron emission tomography																		
qMRI-BIDS	- for quantitative MRI data																		
DICOM ²¹⁵	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine, a standard for medical imaging-based modelling; stores the data as 2D layers																		
CifTI-2 ²¹⁶	Connectivity Informatics Technology Initiative (grayordinate surface + volume)																		
GiftI ²¹⁷	Geometry (surface) file format																		
IBSI ²¹⁸	Image Biomarker Standardization Initiative																		
NIfTI-2 ²¹⁹	Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative: 2 nd Version of a special image format for neuroimaging, where the data are stored in a true 3D volume format																		
NIfTI-MRS ²²⁰	extension of NIfTI for magnetic resonance spectroscopy																		

Table 4: Standard formats for electro- and neurophysiology, biosignal and vital sign data

Standard	Description
ECG-XML ²²¹	An XML-based format for electrocardiogram data
EDF / EDF+ ²²²	European Data Format, a format for exchange and storage of multichannel biological and physical signals, e.g., polysomnography
GDF ²²³	General Data Format; for biomedical signals, like e.g., EEG and ECG data

²¹² <https://bids.neuroimaging.io>²¹³ <https://www.incf.org>²¹⁴ https://bids.neuroimaging.io/get_involved.html#extending-the-bids-specification²¹⁵ <https://www.dicomstandard.org>²¹⁶ https://www.nitrc.org/forum/attachment.php?attachid=333&group_id=454&forum_id=1955²¹⁷ <https://www.nitrc.org/projects/gifti/>²¹⁸ <https://theibsi.github.io>²¹⁹ <https://nifti.nih.gov/nifti-2>²²⁰ https://wtclarke.github.io/mrs_nifti_standard/²²¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9565220/>²²² <https://www.edfplus.info>²²³ http://justsolve.archiveteam.org/wiki/General_Data_Format_for_Biosignals

HL7-aECG ²²⁴	HL7-annotated Electrocardiogram; an annotated XML-based format for electrocardiogram data
ISO/IEEE 11073 ²²⁵	A standard for device interoperability of point-of-care medical device communication
MED ²²⁶	Multiscale Electrophysiology Data Format for EEG data
MFER ²²⁷	Medical waveform Format Encoding Rules, a file format for encoding medical waveforms from ECG, ECoG and EEG data
NIX ²²⁸	Neuroscience Information eXchange for neurophysiology data
NSDF ²²⁹	Neuroscience Simulation Data Format based on HDF5
NWB:N 2.0 ²³⁰	Neurodata Without Borders:Neurophysiology for neurophysiology data
OpenEP ²³¹	A cross-platform electroanatomic mapping data format
SCP-ECG ²³²	Standard Communications Protocol for ECG data
SignalML ²³³	An XML-based meta-format for biomedical time series data
VSIR ²³⁴	Vital Signs Information Representation (CEN 13734)
WFDB ²³⁵	WaveForm DataBase format of the PhysioNet (physio.net) repository; a combination of MIT format and EDF / EDF+

Table 5: Standards for genetic sequence variants

Sequence variant format	Description
VCF ²³⁶	Variant Call Format
BCF ²³⁷	Binary Call Format, a binary version of VCF
MAF ²³⁸	Mutation Annotation Format
GVF ²³⁹	Genome Variation Format, an extension of GFF3
GVCF ²⁴⁰	Genomic Variant Call Format
SPDI ²⁴¹	Sequence, Position, Deletion, Insertion
GA4GH-VR ²⁴²	Genome Alliance for Genomics and Health - Variation Representation
HGVS ²⁴³	Human Genome Variation Society, following the HGVS sequence variant nomenclature

²²⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HL7_aECG

²²⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77338.html>

²²⁶ <https://www.medformat.org>

²²⁷ <http://www.mfer.org/en/index.htm>

²²⁸ <http://g-node.github.io/nix/>

²²⁹ <https://github.com/nsdf/nsdf>

²³⁰ <https://www.nwb.org/2019/02/26/nwbn-2-0-final-released/>

²³¹ <https://openep.io>

²³² <https://github.com/topics/scp-ecg>

²³³ <https://braintech.pl/software/svarog/signalml/?lang=en>

²³⁴ <https://standards.iteh.ai/catalog/standards/cen/8f621d17-ffcc-4885-bfb2-ff72df02e7f1/env-13734-2000>

²³⁵ <https://wfdb.readthedocs.io/en/latest/wfdb.html>

²³⁶ <https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035531692-VCF-Variant-Call-Format>

²³⁷ <https://visoca.github.io/SNP-and-genotype-calling/vcfbcf.html>

²³⁸ https://docs.gdc.cancer.gov/Data/File_Formats/MAF_Format/

²³⁹ <http://www.sequenceontology.org/gvf.html>

²⁴⁰ <https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035531812-GVCF-Genomic-Variant-Call-Format>

²⁴¹ <https://api.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/variation/v0/>

²⁴² <https://vrs.ga4gh.org/en/latest/>

²⁴³ <https://varnomen.hgvs.org/bg-material/simple/>

Table 6: Standards for models

Modelling standard	Description										
Antimony ²⁴⁴	A text-based modular model definition language										
BioPAX ²⁴⁵	Biological Pathways eXchange for exchange and visualisation of biological pathway data										
CellML ²⁴⁶	XML-based description and exchange format for cellular models										
FieldML ²⁴⁷	Human Physiome Field Markup Language, an XML-based format using mathematical field descriptions of cells, tissues and organs; can be used to represent finite element models										
MDL ²⁴⁸	Model Description Language for pharmacometric models										
MFAML ²⁴⁹	Metabolic Flux Analysis Markup Language										
MoBi ²⁵⁰	For multiscale physiological modelling and simulation										
MorpheusML ²⁵¹	Format for agent-based multicellular models										
MultiCellDS ²⁵²	MultiCellular Data Standard for centre-based models (CBMs) [Montagud 2021]										
MultiCellML ²⁵³	Standard for agent-based multiscale and multicellular spatial models										
NeuroML v2 ²⁵⁴	Neuroscience eXtensible Markup Language; an XML-based description and exchange format for models in neuroscience with its four parts: Biophysics, ChannelML, MorphML, and NetworkML										
OpenBEL ²⁵⁵	Biological Expression Language, a triple-based (subject-predicate-object) modelling language for representing biological knowledge by causal, correlative, and associative relationships										
PharmML ²⁵⁶	Pharmacometrics Markup Language, an exchange format for pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic models										
PK-Sim ²⁵⁷	Standard model for whole-body physiologically based pharmacokinetic modelling										
SBML ²⁵⁸	Systems Biology Markup Language, an XML-based description and exchange format for differential-equation models of biological processes. SBML Level 3 is a modular format with a core and packages for extending that core functionality: <table border="1" data-bbox="507 1384 1385 1641"> <tbody> <tr> <td>SBML-arrays</td> <td>- for vectorized, e.g., grid-based models</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SBML-comb</td> <td>- for multiscale and modular, e.g., tissue and whole-body models</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SBML-distrib</td> <td>- for distributions, e.g., systems pharmacology and population models</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SBML-dyn</td> <td>- for dynamical models</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SBML-fbc</td> <td>- for constraint-based flux-balance (steady</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	SBML-arrays	- for vectorized, e.g., grid-based models	SBML-comb	- for multiscale and modular, e.g., tissue and whole-body models	SBML-distrib	- for distributions, e.g., systems pharmacology and population models	SBML-dyn	- for dynamical models	SBML-fbc	- for constraint-based flux-balance (steady
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²⁴⁴ <https://tellurium.readthedocs.io/en/latest/antimony.html>²⁴⁵ <http://www.biopax.org>²⁴⁶ <https://www.cellml.org>²⁴⁷ <https://physiomeproject.org/software/fieldml>²⁴⁸ <http://mdl.community>²⁴⁹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15905275/>²⁵⁰ <https://github.com/Open-Systems-Pharmacology/MoBi>²⁵¹ <https://morpheus.gitlab.io/tag/morpheusml/>²⁵² <http://multicelllds.org>²⁵³ <https://multicellml.org/wiki/doku.php>²⁵⁴ <https://neuroml.org>²⁵⁵ <https://github.com/OpenBEL>²⁵⁶ <https://www.ddmore.foundation/our-standards/>²⁵⁷ <https://github.com/Open-Systems-Pharmacology/PK-Sim>²⁵⁸ <https://sbml.org>

	state), e.g., genome-scale models
	SBML-groups - for grouping and organization
	SBML-layout - for visualization
	SBML-math - support for full MathML
	SBML-multi - for rule-based, e.g., multistate molecules and multicomponent complexed
	SBML-qual - for qualitative (i.e., Boolean) models
	SBML-render - for visualization
	SBML-spatial - for spatial, e.g., reaction-diffusion models
SBOL ²⁵⁹	Synthetic Biology Open Language, describing the exchange of synthetic biological genetic parts, devices, modules, and systems.
SONATA ²⁶⁰	Scalable Open Network Architecture TemplAtE; for large-scale modelling of neuronal brain network models and simulation output
VCML ²⁶¹	Virtual Cell Markup Language for rule-based modelling

Table 7: Standards for model simulations and documentation of results

Standard	Description
GSP ²⁶²	Toward Good Simulation Practice, a proposed quality standard for in silico simulations, developed by the Avicenna Alliance
NuML ²⁶³	Numerical Markup Language, an XML-based format for exchanging numerical data
OMEX ²⁶⁴	Open modelling EXchange for exchange of modelling and simulation data. An OMEX file is a .zip container containing a manifest file, an optional metadata file and the data files.
SBRML ²⁶⁵	Systems Biology Results Markup Language for encoding results of SBML simulations
SED-ML ²⁶⁶	Simulation Experiment Description, a XML-based exchange format for encoding of simulation setups following the MIASE guidelines.

Table 8: Terminologies and ontologies for the description and annotation of data, models, and their components

Ontology	Description
ACGT ²⁶⁷ -MO	Advancing Clinico-genomic Trials on Cancer - Master Ontology
AEO ²⁶⁸	Anatomical Entity Ontology
BCTEO ²⁶⁹	Bone/Cartilage Tissue Engineering Ontology
BRICKS ²⁷⁰	Describes recurring concept in SBGN models
CARO ²⁷¹	Common Anatomy Reference Ontology

²⁵⁹ <https://sbolstandard.org>

²⁶⁰ <https://docs.sonata-project.org/en/master/>

²⁶¹ https://vcell.org/webstart/VCell_Tutorials/VCell_Help/topics/ch_1/Introduction/Export.html

²⁶² <https://insilico.world/sito/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Position-Paper-GSP-R6.pdf>

²⁶³ <https://github.com/NuML/NuML>

²⁶⁴ <https://co.mbine.org/author/combine-archive/>

²⁶⁵ <https://sbrml.sourceforge.net/SBRML/Welcome.html>

²⁶⁶ <https://sed-ml.org>

²⁶⁷ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ACGT-MO/?p=summary>

²⁶⁸ <http://obofoundry.org/ontology/aeo.html>

²⁶⁹ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/BCTEO>

²⁷⁰ <https://brickschema.org/ontology/>

²⁷¹ <http://obofoundry.org/ontology/caro.html>

CBO ²⁷²	The Cell Behavior Ontology is designed to describe multi-cell computational models
CheBI ²⁷³	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest
CO ²⁷⁴	Cell Ontology
CLO ²⁷⁵	Cell Line Ontology
CMDO ²⁷⁶	Clinical MetaData Ontology used for annotation of Common Data Elements (CDEs)
CNO ²⁷⁷	Computational Neuroscience Ontology
CO ²⁷⁸	Cell Ontology
COMODI ²⁷⁹	COmputational MOdels Differ, an ontology to characterise differences in versions of computational biology models
CVDO ²⁸⁰	Cardiovascular Disease Ontology
DEB ²⁸¹	Devices, Experimental Scaffolds, and Biomaterials Ontology
DINTO ²⁸²	Drug-drug Interaction Ontology
DO ²⁸³	Disease ontology
DPV ²⁸⁴	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DQV ²⁸⁵	Data Quality Vocabulary
DTO ²⁸⁶	Drug Target Ontology
DUO ²⁸⁷	Data Use Ontology
ECTO ²⁸⁸	Environmental Conditions, Treatments, and exposures Ontology
EDAM ²⁸⁹	EMBRACE Data and Methods ontology
EnzymeML ²⁹⁰	XML-based format for storage and transfer of enzyme kinetics data
FMA ²⁹¹	Foundational Model of Anatomy for localising anatomical structures at a specific spatial location
FNO ²⁹²	Function ontology
HPO ²⁹³	Human Phenotype Ontology
HUPSON ²⁹⁴	Human Physiology Simulation Ontology containing concepts for simulations, models, and algorithms
ICO ²⁹⁵	Informed Consent Ontology

²⁷² <https://cbo.biocomplexity.indiana.edu>

²⁷³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi>

²⁷⁴ <https://obophenotype.github.io/cell-ontology/>

²⁷⁵ <http://obofoundry.org/ontology/clo.html>

²⁷⁶ <https://biokeanos.com/source/Clinical%20MetaData%20Ontology>

²⁷⁷ <https://github.com/INCF/Computational-Neurosciences-Ontology--C.N.O.->

²⁷⁸ <https://www.ontology.co/index.htm>

²⁷⁹ <http://comodi.sems.uni-rostock.de>

²⁸⁰ <https://github.com/OpenLHS/CVDO>

²⁸¹ <https://matportal.org/ontologies/DEB?p=classes>

²⁸² <https://github.com/labda/DINTO>

²⁸³ <https://disease-ontology.org>

²⁸⁴ <https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.0/dpv>

²⁸⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv>

²⁸⁶ <http://drugtargetontology.org>

²⁸⁷ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

²⁸⁸ <http://obofoundry.org/ontology/ecto.html>

²⁸⁹ <https://edamontology.org/page>

²⁹⁰ <https://enzymeml.org>

²⁹¹ <http://sig.biostr.washington.edu/projects/fm/AboutFM.html>

²⁹² <https://fno.io/ontology/index-en.html>

²⁹³ <https://hpo.jax.org/app/>

²⁹⁴ <https://rohan.scai.fraunhofer.de/ontologies/hupson>

²⁹⁵ <https://akswnc7.informatik.uni-leipzig.de/dstreitmatter/archivo/purl.obolibrary.org/obo--ico--owl/2021.06.04-195648/obo--ico--owl type=pyLodeDoc.html>

InChI ²⁹⁶	IUPAC International Chemical Identifier
KISAO ²⁹⁷	Kinetic Simulation Algorithm Ontology for describing simulation algorithms
LiCO ²⁹⁸	Liver case ontology
MAMO ²⁹⁹	Mathematical Modelling Ontology
MAxO ³⁰⁰	Medical Action Ontology
MELLO ³⁰¹	Medical LifeLog Ontology
MONDO ³⁰²	A semi-automatically constructed ontology defined by the Monarch initiative that merges multiple disease ontologies to yield a coherent merged ontology.
ND ³⁰³	Neurological Disease Ontology
NDD-CTO ³⁰⁴	Clinical Trial Ontology - Neurodegenerative Diseases
NPO ³⁰⁵	NanoParticle Ontology
NPU ³⁰⁶	Nomenclature for Properties and Units terminology
OBCS ³⁰⁷	Ontology of Biological and Clinical Statistics
OBI ³⁰⁸	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations
OGMS ³⁰⁹	Ontology for General Medical Science
OPB ³¹⁰	Ontology of Physics for Biology containing physics concepts to describe the dynamics of biological systems
OPMI ³¹¹	Ontology of Precision Medicine and Investigation
OPS ³¹²	Ontology for Parametric systems
ORDO ³¹³	Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology
PAV ³¹⁴	Ontology for provenance, authoring and versioning
PK ontology ³¹⁵	An ontology for pharmacokinetic models
PMO ³¹⁶	Precision Medicine Ontology
PreMedOnto ³¹⁷	Precision Medicine Ontology
ProbOnto ³¹⁸	Probability Distribution Ontology
ROO ³¹⁹	Radiation Oncology Ontology
SBO ³²⁰	Systems Biology Ontology with terms useful for describing computational modelling

²⁹⁶ <https://iupac.org/who-we-are/divisions/division-details/inchi/>

²⁹⁷ <https://github.com/SED-ML/KiSAO/>

²⁹⁸ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/LICO?p=classes&conceptid=root>

²⁹⁹ <https://sourceforge.net/projects/mamo-ontology/>

³⁰⁰ <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/MAxO>

³⁰¹ <http://mello.snubi.org>

³⁰² <https://mondo.monarchinitiative.org>

³⁰³ <https://github.com/addiehl/neurological-disease-ontology>

³⁰⁴ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/CTO-NDD>

³⁰⁵ <http://www.nano-ontology.org>

³⁰⁶ <https://ifcc.org/ifcc-scientific-division/sd-committees/c-npu/>

³⁰⁷ <https://github.com/obcs/obcs>

³⁰⁸ <https://obi-ontology.org>

³⁰⁹ <https://github.com/OGMS>

³¹⁰ <http://sig.biostr.washington.edu/projects/biosim/opb-intro.html>

³¹¹ <https://github.com/OPMI/opmi>

³¹² <https://www.projekt-scope.de/ontologies/ops/>

³¹³ <https://www.orphadata.com/ontologies/>

³¹⁴ <https://pav-ontology.github.io/pav/>

³¹⁵ <http://rweb.compbio.iupui.edu/corpus/ontology>

³¹⁶ <http://www.phoc.org.cn/pmo/>

³¹⁷ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/PREMEDONTO>

³¹⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/probonto>

³¹⁹ <https://www.cancerdata.org/roo-information>

³²⁰ <https://github.com/EBI-BioModels/SBO>

SBOL-VO ³²¹	Synthetic Biology Open Language Visual Ontology
SIO ³²²	Semantic science Integrated Ontology
STATO ³²³	Ontology of Statistical methods
Strenda ³²⁴	Standard for reporting enzymology data
TEDDY ³²⁵	Terminology for the Description of Dynamics. An Ontology for the description of control elements and dynamics in systems biology and synthetic biology
UCUM ³²⁶	Unified Code for Units of Measure, defined by the Regenstrief institute

Table 9: Clinical languages, terminologies, and code systems

Language, terminology / code system	Description
Arden syntax ³²⁷	a HL7 standard for the representation of medical knowledge, e.g., for use by CDSSs
ATC ³²⁸	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical code, a classification system for the active substances of biomedical drugs
CDS Hooks ³²⁹	“hook”-based pattern for Clinical Decision Support
CQL ³³⁰	Clinical Quality Language, a HL 7 standard for the expression of clinical knowledge used for CDS and electronic Clinical Quality Measurement (eCQM); can also be used for querying complementing FHIR search
EMDN ³³¹	European Medical Device Nomenclature
GMDN ³³²	Global Medical Device Nomenclature
ICD-11 ³³³	International Classification of Diseases
ICF ³³⁴	International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health
ICHI ³³⁵	International Classification of Health Interventions
LOINC ³³⁶	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes for reporting laboratory test results
MedDRA ³³⁷	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
NCIt ³³⁸	the National Cancer Institute thesaurus
ORDO ³³⁹	Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology

³²¹ <https://sbolstandard.org/sbol-visual-ontology/>

³²² <https://github.com/MaastrichtU-IDS/semanticscience>

³²³ <https://stato-ontology.org>

³²⁴ <https://www.beilstein-institut.de/en/projects/strenda/>

³²⁵ <https://www.projekt-scope.de/ontologies/tdy/>

³²⁶ <https://ucum.nlm.nih.gov>

³²⁷ https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=2

³²⁸ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/glossary/atc-code>

³²⁹ <https://cds-hooks.org>

³³⁰ <https://cql.hl7.org>

³³¹ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/dyna2/emdn/>

³³² <https://www.gmdnagency.org>

³³³ <https://icd.org>

³³⁴ <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/international-classification-of-functioning-disability-and-health>

³³⁵ <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/international-classification-of-health-interventions>

³³⁶ <https://loinc.org>

³³⁷ <https://www.meddra.org/>

³³⁸ <https://ncithesaurus.nci.nih.gov/ncitbrowser/>

³³⁹ <https://www.orpha.net/consor/cgi-bin/index.php?lng=EN>

ORPHAcode ³⁴⁰	Encoding of rare diseases and orphan drugs
RadLex ³⁴¹	A structured vocabulary of radiology terms
RxNorm ³⁴²	Normalised Names for clinical drugs
SMART on FHIR ³⁴³	Substitutable Medical Applications and Reusable Technology for Clinical Decision Support
SNOMED-CT ³⁴⁴	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
TNM ³⁴⁵	Tumour Node Metastasis, a classification system for malignant tumours
UMDNS ³⁴⁶	Universal Medical Device Nomenclature System of ECRI institute

Table 10: General metadata standards, formats, and protocols

CERIF ³⁴⁷	Common European Research Information Format <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A conceptual model describing the Research domain. • defined as Entity Relationship Model (ERM).
DCAT ³⁴⁸ -AP 3	Data CATalogue 3 – Application Profile: is a RDF-vocabulary defined by the W3C to facilitate interoperability between data catalogues on the web.
healthDCAT-AP ³⁴⁹	Metadata standard for supporting interoperability of health data in the EHDS ³⁵⁰ (European Health DataSpace). The HealthDCAT-AP editor ³⁵¹ is a tool for creating datasets compliant to healthDCAT-AP.
METS ³⁵²	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for encoding descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata regarding objects within a digital library. • defined as XML schema.
OAI-PMH ³⁵³	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A protocol developed for harvesting metadata descriptions of records in an archive to achieve repository interoperability. • defined as a set of six web requests or HTML verbs: GetRecord, Identify, ListIdentifiers, ListMetadataFormats, ListRecords, ListSets
XMP ³⁵⁴	Extensible Metadata Platform (ISO 16684-1:2019) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contains the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data model: the structure of statements that XMP can make about resources. - Serialization: how any instance of the XMP data model can be recorded as XML • the embedding of XMP packets in specific file formats and domain specific XMP properties can be freely defined.

³⁴⁰ <https://www.orpha.net/consor/cgi-bin/Disease.php?lng=EN>

³⁴¹ <https://radlex.org>

³⁴² <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/rxnorm/overview.html>

³⁴³ <https://docs.smarthealthit.org>

³⁴⁴ <https://www.snomed.org>

³⁴⁵ <https://www.uicc.org/resources/tnm>

³⁴⁶ <https://www.ecri.org/solutions/umdns>

³⁴⁷ https://eurocris.org/eurocris_archive/cerifsupport.org

³⁴⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3>

³⁴⁹ <https://healthcat-ap.github.io>

³⁵⁰ <https://www.european-health-data-space.com>

³⁵¹ <http://fair.healthdataportal.eu/editor2>

³⁵² <https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/mets-home.html>

³⁵³ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh>

³⁵⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/75163.html>

OpenAIRE Metadata format ³⁵⁵	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • expects the metadata to be encoded in the DataCite metadata format. • uses the OAI-PMH v2.0 protocol for harvesting dataset metadata.
DataCite Metadata Schema V4.4 ³⁵⁶	For publication and citation of research data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes. • The metadata of Invenio³⁵⁷ are aligned with the DataCite metadata schema.

Table 11: Alternative model and data quality criteria

Quality criteria	Description
Accessibility	Are the data available for authorized persons?
Applicability	Can the model be used in the defined CoU for the QoI?
Composability	System design principle that allows to integrate submodels into models on a higher scale. The composability depends on the inter-relationships of the components. Using small interfaces enhances the integrability and composability.
Consistency	Consistency across datasets and over time.
Controllability	Ability to move a system around in its entire configuration space . Dual to Observability.
Credibility	The trust in the predictive capability of the used computational model for the defined context of use.
Identifiability	A model is identifiable, if it is theoretically possible to learn the true values of this model's underlying parameters after obtaining an infinite number of observations from it (parameter observability). If a model is not identifiable, then the data can be generated by multiple different parameter assignments to the model.
Explainability	Ability of the parameters, often hidden in Deep Nets, to justify the results.
Generalizability	Means the optimal balance between underfitting and overfitting; can be reached e.g. by regularization, cross-validation, data augmentation and normalization, feature engineering and ensemble methods.
Interpretability	How accurate a machine learning model can associate a cause to an effect.
Observability	A measure of how well internal states of a system can be inferred from knowledge of its external outputs.
Portability	Can the model easily be installed, replaced or moved from one system to another?
Transparency	Means that a model has its state expressed in some form that one can understand. One can distinguish model transparency, design transparency, algorithmic transparency etc. Includes also the data retention and expiration policies.
Repeatability	Measures the measurement variation by the same instrument or person under the same conditions.
Reproducibility	Considers the results of experiments conducted by different individuals, at different locations, with different instruments. Requires a detailed description of the used parameters, initial and

³⁵⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu>³⁵⁶ <https://schema.datacite.org>³⁵⁷ <https://inveniosoftware.org>

	boundary conditions. For assessing the reproducibility [Tiwari et al., 2021] proposed a reproducibility scorecard comprising 8 points to ensure model reproducibility. [Porubsky et al., 2020] define best practices to build reproducible models.
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Table 12: Recommendations for predictive computational models in personalised medicine research – Guidelines for validating models according to ISO/TS 9491-1

Model type	Recommendation
Cellular Systems biology models	1. A standardised protocol for patient history and information should be developed and integrated with clinical standard protocols, e.g., electronic health records (EHRs) and FHIR.
	2. The use of patient expression profile e.g., mRNA or protein expression, should be agreed upon.
	3. Prediction models with a fitting hypothesis should be developed.
	4. Model replication and reproduction should be used before considering clinical trials.
	5. Model predictions (e.g., biomarkers selection) should be compared with established clinical ones.
	6. User-friendly graphical interfaces should be developed to ease the use of models in clinics.
Risk prediction for common diseases	1. The highest possible diversity needed sample sizes for all the genetic studies on complex diseases as well as for performing functional studies should be ensured.
	2. The development of relevant transparent, standardised, and detailed methods clearly stating methodological choices made with necessary justifications to enhance reproducible research should be enabled.
Disease course and therapy response prediction	1. Disease specific scores including objective parameters of disease activity and progression should be harmonised.
	2. The development and validation of innovative patient-reported outcome tools for clinical trials including the safe and easy use of app- and wearable-based technologies should be supported.
	3. Minimum clinical criteria for a systems medicine trial combined using harmonised scores and quantitative, validated patient reported outcomes into account should be defined.
	4. Concepts for integrating model-based prediction and AI content into curricular education in medicine and medical life sciences should be developed.
	5. Stakeholder discussions including political decision makers to overcome financial and intellectual hurdles in large European consortium trials, ideally involving both academic and European industry partners (current schemes of the Innovative Medicine Initiative can serve as a starting point) should be commenced.
	6. New models of public-private partnerships for a strong European health care economy on IP participation and protection of mutual interests should be developed.
Pharmacokinetic / -dynamic modelling and in silico trial simulations	1. Appropriate in vitro-in vivo extrapolations from targeted assays to aid in validating PK/PD models (a full validation of PK/PD models requires comprehensive measurements of drug PK as well as of the resulting therapeutic effect) should be developed.

	2. An agreement among relevant stakeholders on required criteria for model adequacy for a well-defined context of use should be implemented.
	3. It should be ensured that the standards (to be) used for model development, evaluation, reporting and related decision making are commonly acknowledged by all the involved parties (regulators, HTA (Health Technology Assessment) agencies, academia, research centres, industry, and patient organisations) are relevant for all the types of models that can be used.
	4. The requirements for adequate implementation of the two other components (patient's and other design characteristics) should also be standardised and discussed by the involved stakeholders.
Artificial intelligence	1. Model validation should involve a 3-phase process.
	2. In the first phase, outcome prediction for the AI model should be compared to standard measures that employ best clinical practice and using established evidence-based hierarchy which considers historical practice, clinical trials, and systematic review / meta-analyses.
	3. If the AI model shows a predictive advantage, a second phase of validation should involve use of a High Confidence Off Policy Evaluation as previously described where the AI model is compared to clinician decision making.
	4. If beneficial, phase 3 should provide clinicians access to AI prediction points.

Table 13: Clinical interoperability standards

Interoperability standard	Description
BRIDG ³⁵⁸	Biomedical Research Integrated Domain Group for the integration with preclinical research data
CDISC OMOP CDM ³⁵⁹	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium – Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model
DCM ³⁶⁰	Detailed Clinical Model
EEHRxF ³⁶¹	European Electronic Health Record eXchange Format
FHIM ³⁶²	Federated Health Information Model
HL7 V3 CDA ³⁶³	Health Level 7 – Clinical Document Architecture
HL7 FHIR ³⁶⁴	Health Level 7 – Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
IHE XDS ³⁶⁵	Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise - Cross-Enterprise Document Sharing
OpenEHR ³⁶⁶	Open Electronic Health Record

³⁵⁸ <https://bridgmodel.nci.nih.gov>³⁵⁹ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization>³⁶⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79498.html>³⁶¹ <https://www.x-ehealth.eu/eehrxf>³⁶² <https://fhim.org>³⁶³ <https://hl7.org/cda/stds/core>³⁶⁴ <https://hl7.org/fhir>³⁶⁵ https://wiki.ihe.net/index.php/Cross-Enterprise_Document_Sharing³⁶⁶ <https://openehr.org>